

Polynomial linear recurrences over the powers

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Abstract

The aim of this paper ¹ is to state fundamental algebraic linear recurrent relations which characterize polynomials. The Discrete Fourier Transform, Cauchy's theorems from analytical functions, Girard-Newton formulas as well as the fundamental theorem of Algebra are derived from these algebraic relations. The discrete mean theorem, the discrete Cauchy's theorems and discrete Poisson formulas are introduced for polynomials as analogous of their continuous version for analytical or harmonic functions. The results are also extended to multivariate polynomials. Moreover, the linearity of relations engaged in the process let us elaborate numerical methods to solve various problems in algebra as euclidean division, GCD or exact rational reconstruction, and numerical analysis with polynomial or rational interpolation and approximation. In order to follow the evolution of this work, a paragraph at the end of the document lists the changes brought by the current iteration.

1 Introduction

In 1625, in a booklet entitled *Inventiones Nouvelles en l'Algèbre* [6]², Albert Girard has sowed the germs of the development of the sums of the powers of the roots in terms of the coefficients of a polynomial equation. In *Arithmetica universalis*, written after 1673, Isaac Newton put forward a more precise formulation of these power-sum formulas, without any proof. Many proofs, mentioned in the survey of the subject [11], have since been proposed for these formulas. In the literature their importance is mostly emphasized in the basis change method as stated by the fundamental theorem of symmetric polynomials [4], for combinatorics [2] or for abstract algebra and representation theory [5, 8]. But, if these relations are not, to our knowledge, used or even clearly viewed as a linear recurrence of the polynomial sum on successive powers, they certainly represent the oldest manifestation of recurrences of polynomials on successive powers. When we produce a polynomial interpolation we can be very surprised by the inherent rigidity of polynomials thru the Runge phenomenon [13], revealing a local global paradox and leaving one suspecting an hidden spine in their structure. What is behind this specificity?. The main goal of this paper is to state that all polynomials, univariate or multivariate, satisfy linear recurrence formulas on successive powers, as we can perceive it in Girard-Newton formulas. More precisely, we demonstrate that constraints of linear recurrent values on successive powers is also a characteristic of the ring of polynomials. In the complex domain, we then establish the link between the Discrete Fourier Transform and polynomial linear recurrences. We prove a discrete mean property satisfied by polynomials on regular polygons, a discrete analog of the mean theorem for analytical functions. We also obtain discrete Cauchy's theorems for polynomials, as the discrete versions of the well known theorems for analytical functions, all being translations of more general linear

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²We would like to warmly thank Dr K. van Ommen, curator Western Printed Works & Coordinator of the Scaliger Institute, for allowing us to consult an original version of this booklet in the library of the University of Leiden.

recurrent relations for polynomials on polygons. The Lagrange interpolation is also shown to be able to build the linear recurrence relations. A matrix formulation leads to properties of some Hankel determinants and the diagonalization of the involved matrices. To consolidate the bridge to analytical functions we prove that the Cauchy's theorems for analytical functions are deduced from discrete Cauchy's theorems versions for polynomials. We introduce a formula for computing derivatives and deduce a discrete version of the Morera theorem. Coming back to polynomials we present a discrete version of the maximum principle and a minimum principle, both on polygons. The fundamental theorem of algebra appears then as a straightforward consequence of the discrete minimum principle for polynomials. To give a broader view, a section is devoted to extend previous results to more general paths, where polynomials still satisfy linear recurrences. If this work is, at first, mainly focused on univariate polynomials, the next part shows that recurrence relations are also available for multivariate polynomials. Thus, The Girard-Newton formulas appear as a special case of these recurrences and all symmetric elementary polynomials inherit such recurrent formulas. Most of the properties obtained for univariate polynomials are then extended to the multivariate case. Finally, thru examples, we exhibit some methods to solve various problems in algebra and numerical analysis. With the help of polynomial linear recurrent relations, we can effectively obtain solutions for the polynomial euclidean division, the greatest common divisor, exact reconstruction of rational functions, rational interpolation and rational uniform approximations.

The essence of this work being based on the vault of linear recurrences and the pillars of elementary symmetric polynomials, we recall here the main ingredients of these theories that will cement the structure.

2 Elementary symmetric polynomials and linear recurrences

2.1 Notations

We denote by $C_{0,1}$ the unitary circle in \mathbb{C} . For n variables, $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, and any integer $1 \leq k \leq n$ we note $\sigma_{k,n}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ the elementary symmetric polynomials

$$\sigma_{k,n}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq n} x_{i_1} x_{i_2} \dots x_{i_k}. \quad (1)$$

We are mostly interested by the particular case where $x_i = x_0^i$ for a fixed $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ or \mathbb{C} . We will use the univariate polynomials defined for $1 \leq k \leq n$ and $0 \leq i \leq n$ by

$${}_i\sigma_{k,n}(x_0) = \sigma_{k,n}\left(1, x_0, x_0^2, \dots, x_0^{i-1}, x_0^{i+1}, \dots, x_0^n\right), \quad (2)$$

that is to say, the k -th elementary symmetric polynomial where we use the successive powers of the same fixed number, except that we omit the i -th power. When there is no prescript, it means that all the successive powers are considered from 0 up to n and for $1 \leq k \leq n + 1$

$$\sigma_{k,n+1}(x_0) = \sum_{0 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq n} x_0^{\sum_{s=1}^k i_s}. \quad (3)$$

These functions are polynomials in x_0 with integer coefficients. Coefficients count the number of ways we can choose k distinct integers smaller or equal to n to obtain the same sum.

Let's introduce now the classic background around elementary symmetric polynomials and linear recurrences in conjunction with polynomials.

2.2 Polynomials and elementary symmetric functions

The relationship, also known as Viète's rules,

$$\prod_{i=1}^n (x - \lambda_i) = x^n + \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-k} \sigma_{n-k,n}(\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n) x^k \quad (4)$$

establishes the link between the coefficients and the roots for a polynomial and will be mainly used in the context where the roots are powers of the same number. Introduced first by Viète in the restrictive case of positive roots, they were extended as a general principle by Girard.

We also recall now the necessary background related to linear recurrences in \mathbb{C} or \mathbb{R} .

2.3 Polynomials and linear recurrences

A sequence $(a_n)_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$, of numbers in \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} , is said to satisfy a linear recurrence, with given coefficients c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n in \mathbb{R} (or \mathbb{C} respectively), if

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, \sum_{i=0}^{i=n} c_i a_{i+k} = 0.$$

It can be easily checked that the set of all solutions of a given linear recurrence is a vectorial subspace of the vectorial space of sequences in \mathbb{R} (or \mathbb{C} respectively). Since the recurrence formula with $n+1$ terms determines a unique solution sequence as soon as n consecutive terms are given, we can restrict our description of the set of solutions to the n first terms of the different solutions. In this way, it appears a natural basis of the subspace of the solutions of one linear recurrence. Indeed, if we consider for each $j \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, the solution sequence $(a_{j,n})_{n \in \mathbb{Z}}$ generated by n first terms of the form,

$$a_{j,i} = \delta_j(i) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{iff } 0 \leq i \leq n-1, i \neq j \\ 1 & \text{iff } i = j \end{cases}$$

then the different sequences are linearly independent and they form a generating family of the vectorial subspace of the solutions. Thus we have a basis of the solutions, and the vectorial space of the solutions is of dimension n . This basis is not very informative about the general form of the terms of the solutions. A more comprehensive description can be obtained by considering a basis formed by solutions with explicit formula for every terms. By asking that a solution is, for some λ , of the form,

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{Z}, a_n = \lambda^n,$$

we are led to the polynomial constraint,

$$\sum_{i=0}^n c_i \lambda^i = 0.$$

It means that λ is a root of the polynomial $P_c(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n c_i x^i$, which is called the characteristic polynomial of the linear recurrence. In the particular case where P_c has n **distinct** roots $\{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n\}$, we obtain a new basis of the vectorial subspace of the solutions. Any solution of the recurrence can then be written as a linear combination of the form,

$$a_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \lambda_i^n,$$

for some coefficients $(\alpha_i)_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ that can be computed from the knowledge of n consecutive terms.

We will use this result extensively but in a slightly different way.

3 Algebraic foundations of polynomial linear power recurrences

The first recurrent relation for polynomials we deploy is a limited version, restricted to polynomials with no constant term. Beginning by this, we can derive two other more general recurrent relations, with two different strategies.

Theorem 1 (The polynomial homogeneous linear recurrence) *Any real (complex) polynomial $P(x)$ such that $P(0) = 0$ and of degree less than or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}$, satisfies the linear recurrences,*

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P\left(x_0^{n+k}\right) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) P\left(x_0^{i+k}\right) = 0. \quad (5)$$

Proof.

Let's take a look at three elementary cases.

For $x_0 = 0$, the recurrence is obvious, since $P(0^k) = 0$ for $k \neq 0$ and else ${}_0\sigma_{n,n}(0) = 0$.

For $x_0 = 1$ and $i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$, we have ${}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(1) = C_n^{n-i}$. The left member of the recurrence, where each $P(x_0^{k+i}) = 1$, becomes with the help of the binomial formula of Newton

$$\begin{aligned} P(1) \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n-i} C_n^{n-i} &= P(1) \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^i C_n^i \\ &= P(1) \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^i (1)^{n-i} C_n^i \\ &= P(1) (1-1)^n = 0. \end{aligned}$$

For $x_0 = -1$, the coefficients ${}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(-1)$ of the recurrence are the coefficients of the polynomial with roots $(-1)^i$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$,

$$t^n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) t^i.$$

If $n = 2p$, this polynomial can be written

$$\prod_{i=1}^{i=n} (t - (-1)^i) = \prod_{i=1}^{i=p} (t^2 - 1) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i t^{2(p-i)}.$$

The coefficient of t^i in the polynomial corresponds to the coefficient of $P(x_0^{i+k})$ in the recurrence, but we have only even powers of t . We observe $P(x_0^{2i+k}) = P((-1)^k)$ and it can be factored. The left member of the recurrence is thus

$$P((-1)^k) \sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i = 0.$$

If $n = 2p + 1$, the associated polynomial to the coefficients of the recurrence can be written

$$\begin{aligned} \prod_{i=1}^{i=n} (t - (-1)^i) &= (t+1) \prod_{i=1}^{i=p} (t^2 - 1) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i t^{2(p-i)+1} + \sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i t^{2(p-i)}. \end{aligned}$$

We use that $P\left(x_0^{2(p-i)+k}\right) = P((-1)^k)$ and $P\left(x_0^{2(p-i)+1+k}\right) = P((-1)^{k+1})$ and the left member of the recurrence is now

$$\sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i P(x_0^{2(p-i)+1}) + \sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i P(x_0^{2(p-i)}) = (P((-1)^k) + P((-1)^{k+1})) \sum_{i=0}^{i=p} C_p^i (-1)^i = 0.$$

Now, we set $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^* \setminus \{1; -1\}$ or $x_0 \in \mathbb{C}^* \setminus C_{0,1}$ to ensure that successive powers of x_0 are all distinct. We replace formally $P(x_0^s) = a_s$ in the recurrent relation. The sequence $(a_s)_{s \in \mathbb{Z}}$ is now the solution of the linear recurrent relation

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, a_{n+k} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) a_{k+i} = 0. \quad (6)$$

The sequences that are solutions of a linear recurrent relation are obtained by studying the characteristic polynomial $P_c(x)$ associated to the linear recurrence, as we previously do implicitly in the particular cases. $P_c(x)$ is defined by

$$P_c(x) = x^n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) x^i. \quad (7)$$

The coefficients of this polynomial are the symmetric functions of its roots, up to a change of sign. But, the coefficients are exactly, up to a change of sign, the symmetric functions of $\{x_0, x_0^2, \dots, x_0^n\}$, hence

$$P_c(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n (x - x_0^i).$$

Since then, the roots being distinct, the sequences solutions are all linear combinations of the form

$$a_k = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \alpha_i \times (x_0^i)^k$$

where the α_i are any coefficients that completely determine a solution. The key is that a_k can be rewritten as a polynomial in x_0^k , if we exchange the order of powers

$$a_k = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \alpha_i \times (x_0^k)^i = Q(x_0^k),$$

where $Q(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \alpha_i x^i$ is finally any polynomial of degree less than or equal to n such that $Q(0) = 0$. Therefore, all polynomials of degree less than or equal to n satisfy the recurrent relation for any $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^* \setminus \{1; -1\}$ or $x_0 \in \mathbb{C}^* \setminus C_{0,1}$.

To overcome the case when $x_0 \in C_{0,1}$, we can reason by continuity. The functions ${}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0)$ are polynomials in x_0 , and so continuous everywhere. For any polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , if we take a sequence of numbers $(x_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ outside $C_{0,1}$ and which converges to $x_0 \in C_{0,1}$ when j tends to infinity, then, by continuity, the sequence

$$y_j = P(x_j^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_j) P(x_j^{k+i})$$

converges to

$$P(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) P(x_0^{k+i}).$$

All y_j are equal to zero, because x_j are outside $C_{0,1}$ and P satisfy the recurrence relation for each of them. We conclude, by sequential continuity, that

$$P(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) P(x_0^{k+i}) = 0$$

as the limit of the null sequence. ■

Example 1.1 Any polynomial of degree 2, with real coefficients and such that $P(0) = 0$, satisfies

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+2}) = (x_0 + x_0^2)P(x_0^{k+1}) - x_0^3P(x_0^k).$$

Theorem 2 (The affine polynomial recurrence) Any real (complex) polynomial $P(x)$ of degree less than or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}$, satisfies the non homogeneous linear recurrences,

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0)P(x_0^{k+i}) - \pi_n(x_0)P(0) = 0. \quad (8)$$

where $\pi_n(x_0) = \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - x_0^i)$.

Proof.

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We then set,

$$Q(x) = P(x) - P(0).$$

$Q(x)$ satisfy the hypotheses of theorem 1, and so the associated homogeneous linear recurrence.

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, Q(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0)Q(x_0^{k+i}) = 0.$$

Replacing $Q(x)$ by its counterpart, we have successively,

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+n}) - P(0) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) \left(P(x_0^{k+i}) - P(0) \right) = 0.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0)P(x_0^{k+i}) \\ - P(0) \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) + 1 \right) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Let's focus now on the last term of the expression, without the factor $P(0)$.

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) + 1$$

We recognize the value for $x = 1$ of the polynomial

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) x^i + x^n.$$

From the symmetric functions which constitute the coefficients, we observe that the roots of this polynomial are $\{x_0, x_0^2, \dots, x_0^n\}$. This allows us to write the factorized form

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) x^i + x^n = \prod_{i=1}^n (x - x_0^i). \quad (9)$$

When we evaluate (9) in $x = 1$, we find the last term of the recurrent formula. Let's notice that the recurrence is no more linear, but the constant term invites us to qualify it as affine. ■

Example 2.1 Any polynomial of degree 2 satisfies

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z},$$

$$P(x_0^{k+2}) = (x_0 + x_0^2)P(x_0^{k+1}) - x_0^3P(x_0^k) + (x_0^3 - x_0^2 - x_0 + 1)P(0).$$

And with a more specific value $x_0 = 3$, we have

Example 2.2 Any polynomial of degree 2 satisfies

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(3^{k+2}) = 12P(3^{k+1}) - 27P(3^k) + 16P(0).$$

Theorem 3 (The general polynomial linear recurrence) Any real (complex) polynomial $P(x)$ of degree less than or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}$, satisfies the homogeneous linear recurrences

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R} \text{ (or } \mathbb{C}), \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+n+1}) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) P(x_0^{k+i}) = 0. \quad (10)$$

Proof. We suppose that x_0 is real and $x_0 \notin \{-1, 0, 1\}$, or is complex and $x_0 \in \mathbb{C}^* \setminus C_{0,1}$, which ensures that the powers of x_0 are all distinct numbers. Following the same demonstration as in the theorem 2, we replace formally $P(x_0^k) = a_k$, and the sequence $(a_k)_{k \in \mathbb{Z}}$ must check the recurrence,

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, a_{k+n+1} + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) a_{k+i} = 0$$

The characteristic polynomial associated to the recurrence is now,

$$P_c(x) = x^{n+1} + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) x^i.$$

The roots of this polynomial are, this time, the $n + 1$ numbers $\{1, x_0, x_0^2, \dots, x_0^n\}$.

$$P_c(x) = \prod_{i=0}^n (x - x_0^i)$$

The sequences solutions of the recurrence are then all the linear combinations of the form,

$$a_k = \sum_{i=0}^{i=n} \alpha_i \times (x_0^i)^k.$$

We can again change the order of powers to recognize a polynomial

$$a_k = \sum_{i=0}^{i=n} \alpha_i \times (x_0^k)^i = Q(x_0^k)$$

where $Q(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=n} \alpha_i x^i$ is any polynomial of degree less than or equal to n . We use the same reasoning to conclude by continuity that the relation also holds for $\{-1, 0, 1\}$ in the real case, or for $C_{0,1} \cup \{0\}$ in the complex case. ■

Example 3.1 Any polynomial of degree 2 satisfies,

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+3}) = (1 + x_0 + x_0^2)P(x_0^{k+2}) - (x_0 + x_0^2 + x_0^3)P(x_0^{k+1}) + x_0^3P(x_0^k).$$

More particularly, with the value $x_0 = 2$, we have

Example 3.2 Any polynomial of degree 2 satisfies

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(2^{k+3}) = 7P(2^{k+2}) - 14P(2^{k+1}) + 8P(2^k).$$

The general linear recurrence satisfied by polynomials is a characteristic of the degree of the polynomial. It is time to prove that any polynomial of degree greater than n can't satisfy the recurrences elaborated for the degree n . But polynomials of degree n satisfy all recurrences satisfied by polynomials of greater degree.

Theorem 4 (A characterization of the degree)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree p strictly greater than n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If we note

$$P(x_0^{k+n+1}) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) P(x_0^{k+i}) = R_k(x_0).$$

then

1. $\forall k \in \mathbb{N}$ there are at most $(k+n+1)p$ values x_0 such that $R_k(x_0) = 0$.
2. $\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ (or \mathbb{C}), there are at most p values k such that $R_k(x_0) = 0$.

Proof. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ and P a polynomial of degree $p > n$. $R_k(x_0)$ is a polynomial in x_0 . Let's look to the degree of each term of the sum. $P(x_0^{k+i})$ has degree $ip + kp$ and so we have x_0^{kp} in factor in the monomial of highest degree of each term. This let us restrict the study of the degree of each term to the case $k = 0$. For $1 \leq s \leq n+1$ the symmetric functions

$$\sigma_{s, n+1}(x_0) = \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_s \leq n+1} x_0^{\sum_{m=1}^s i_m},$$

have their highest degree obtained once, when the $i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_s$ correspond to the s greater consecutive integers up to n . The degree in x_0 is then

$$\deg(\sigma_{s, n+1}(x_0)) = \sum_{i=n-s+1}^n i = s \left(\frac{2n-s+1}{2} \right),$$

and

$$\deg(\sigma_{s, n+1}(x_0) P(x_0^{n+1-s})) = s \left(\frac{2n-s+1}{2} \right) + (n+1-s)p,$$

As a function of s this expression has its maximum for $s_{max} = n - p + \frac{1}{2}$ and with $p \geq n+1$, $s_{max} \leq -\frac{1}{2}$. This ensures that it is a decreasing function of s . The maximum degree in x_0 in the sum is thus for $s = 1$ and is equal to $d_{max} = n + np$. We see that $d_{max} < (n+1)p$ and it says that the degrees in the sum can't reach the degree of $P(x_0^{n+1})$ which is $(n+1)p$. The left member, a polynomial in x_0 with a degree not equal to zero, only have a finit number of roots. The same result occurs for any k , all the powers being translated by kp , the degree is exactly $np + kp + p$ and this is the maximum number of values x_0 which cancel $R_k(x_0)$. This proves the point 1.

Moreover, for a fixed x_0 , the linear recurrences $R_k(x_0) = 0$ has a characteristic polynomial defined by

$$P_c(t) = \prod_{i=0}^n (t - x_0^i)$$

and, as explained previously in theorem (3), there is a polynomial Q_n of degree n ,

$$Q_n(t) = \sum_{i=0}^n q_i t^i,$$

such that the sequence $Q_n(x_0^i)$ is solution of all linear relations $R_k(x_0) = 0$ with starting values $Q_n(x_0^i) = P(x_0^i)$ for $i \in \{0, \dots, n-1\}$. The solution of the recurrence being unique, the expanded form $P(t) = \sum_{i=0}^p p_i t^i$ must comply, for some k , successively to

$$\begin{aligned} P(x_0^k) &= Q_n(x_0^k) \\ \sum_{i=0}^p p_i x_0^{i+k} &= \sum_{i=0}^n q_i x_0^{i+k} \\ \sum_{n+1=0}^p p_i x_0^{i+k} + \sum_{i=0}^n (p_i - q_i) x_0^{i+k} &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

This is the value in x_0^k of the polynomial $C(t)$ of degree p

$$C(t) = \sum_{n+1=0}^p p_i t_0^i + \sum_{i=0}^n (p_i - q_i) t^i.$$

This implies that P checks $R_k(x_0) = 0$ if and only if x_0^k is a root of the polynomial $C(t)$. But $C(t)$ has at most p roots and so there are at most p values of k for which it occurs. This concludes the item 2. ■

Theorem 5 (Polynomial linear recurrences and linear transformations)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any linear transformation, real or complex, $T(x) = ax + b$, we have

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(ax_0^{k+n+1} + b) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) P(ax_0^{k+i} + b) = 0. \quad (11)$$

Proof. The polynomial Q defined by $Q(x) = P(ax + b)$ has the same degree as P , therefore it must satisfy the linear recurrences

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, Q(x_0^{k+n+1}) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) Q(x_0^{k+i}) = 0.$$

The coefficients are completely independent of the choice of the polynomial and are only determined by x_0 . The substitution $Q(x_0^{k+i}) = P(ax_0^{k+i} + b)$ simply complete the proof. ■

These relations are usefull when we need to obtain recurrences for a polynomial P with the values around a value b and another powers scale controlled by a and x_0 . We have connected in (8) the polynomial linear recurrences for a polynomial P with its value in zero $P(0)$ or equivalently to the constant coefficient of the polynomial. Now we extend the process to connect the recurrence relations to the k -th derivatives in zero of the polynomials or equivalently to it's coefficient of power k .

Theorem 6 (The extended polynomial linear recurrences)

Any real (complex) polynomial $P(x)$ of degree less than or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}$, with expanded form

$$P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$$

satisfies for each $s \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ the linear recurrences

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, P(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i, n}(x_0) P(x_0^{k+i}) = a_s x_0^{sk} \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq s}}^{i=n} (x_0^s - x_0^i). \quad (12)$$

Proof. Let's fix $s \in \{0, \dots, n\}$. The polynomial $Q_s(x) = P(x) - a_s x^s$ has no monomial component of degree s . Such polynomials can be reconstituted by a recurrence whose characteristic polynomial has only the n roots $\{x_0^0, x_0^1, \dots, x_0^{s-1}, x_0^{s+1}, \dots, x_0^n\}$. The associated elementary symmetric polynomials are ${}_s\sigma_{i,n}$. The polynomial with those roots is now

$$P_c(t) = \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq s}}^{i=n} (t - x_0^i) = t^n + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) t^i. \quad (13)$$

Going back to the recurrence relations associated to this characteristic polynomial, we obtain that Q must satisfy linear recurrences of the form

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad Q(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) Q(x_0^{k+i}) = 0. \quad (14)$$

Introducing the relation $Q_s(x) = P(x) - a_s x^s$ in the recurrence, we obtain

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}(\mathbb{C}), \forall k \in \mathbb{Z},$$

$$P(x_0^{k+n}) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) P(x_0^{k+i}) - a_s \left((x_0^{k+n})^s + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) (x_0^{k+i})^s \right) = 0.$$

We conclude by observing that

$$\begin{aligned} x_0^{ks} \left(x_0^{sn} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i,n}(x_0) x_0^{si} \right) &= x_0^{ks} P_c(x_0^s) \\ &= x_0^{ks} \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq s}}^{i=n} (x_0^s - x_0^i). \end{aligned}$$

■

Theorem 7 (Extended polynomial linear recurrences and linear transforms)

For any (real) complex polynomial $P(z)$ of degree less or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and any linear transform $T(z) = az + b$ and $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}$, we have for each $s \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ the linear recurrences

$$\begin{aligned} \forall z_0 \in \mathbb{C}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad P\left(T(z_0^{k+n+1})\right) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n-i} {}_s\sigma_{n-i,n}(z_0) P\left(T(z_0^{k+i})\right) \\ = \frac{a^s}{s!} P^{(s)}(b) z_0^{ks} \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq s}}^{i=n} (z_0^s - z_0^i). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Proof. We apply the previous theorem (6) with the polynomial $Q(z) = P(T(z)) = P(az + b)$ which has the same degree. From the interpretation of polynomial coefficients in terms of their derivatives, a_s in the original formula can be expressed as

$$a_s = \frac{Q^{(s)}(0)}{s!}.$$

We compute

$$\frac{Q^{(s)}(0)}{s!} = \frac{(P(az + b))^{(s)}(0)}{s!} = \frac{a^s}{s!} P^{(s)}(b)$$

and we replace in the original recurrence. The coefficients don't change, they only rely on z_0 . ■

Theorem 8 (A characterization of real polynomials by linear recurrences) *Let $f(x)$ be a continuous function on \mathbb{R} . If f satisfies*

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, f\left(x_0^{k+n+1}\right) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(x_0) f\left(x_0^{k+i}\right) = 0, \quad (16)$$

then f is a polynomial of degree less than or equal to n .

Proof.

Let $f(x)$ be a continuous function on \mathbb{R} satisfying all the recurrences (12). Let's take an $x_0 > 1$. There is a unique polynomial P of degree less or equal to n , solution of the recurrences (12). Thus f is equal to P on all x_0^i , $i \in \mathbb{Z}$. Now we watch what happens on rational powers of x_0 . Let $q \in \mathbb{N}^*$ and we consider the recurrence for $x_0^{\frac{1}{q}}$. There is a polynomial P_2 equal to f on all integral powers of $x_0^{\frac{1}{q}}$. In particular, for every integer $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$, we have

$$f\left(\left(x_0^{\frac{1}{q}}\right)^{mq}\right) = P_2\left(\left(x_0^{\frac{1}{q}}\right)^{mq}\right) = f\left(x_0^m\right) = P_1\left(x_0^m\right) = P_2\left(x_0^m\right).$$

P_1 and P_2 coincide on an infinity of distinct values and are so identical. Since it is true for any choice of q , f and P_1 are equal on all x_0^a with $a \in \mathbb{Q}_+^*$. With $\log(x_0) > 1$, where \log designates the natural logarithm, the function

$$g(\alpha) = x_0^\alpha = e^{\alpha \log(x_0)}$$

is continuous from $[0, +\infty[$ to $[1, +\infty[$, thus the density of \mathbb{Q}_+^* in \mathbb{R}_+^* implies the density of positive rational powers of x_0 in $[1, +\infty[$. f and P_1 being equal on this dense set, they are equal on the whole set $[1, +\infty[$ by continuity. Considering now $0 < x_0 < 1$, the same function g , with $\log(x_0)$, produces a continuous mapping from $[0, +\infty[$ to $]0, 1[$, and using the same reasoning with density and continuity, there is a polynomial P_3 equal to f on $]0, 1[$. But f and P_1 are also equal on an infinity of values in $]0, 1[$, when we use the recurrence for x_0 in $[1, +\infty[$ and negative integral powers x_0^{-i} for $i \in \mathbb{N}^*$. Then P_3 and P_1 are equal everywhere. f and P_1 are now equal on \mathbb{R}_+^* and, by continuity in 0, on \mathbb{R}_+ . If we use a value $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}_-^*$, $x_0 \neq -1$, there is a polynomial P_4 such that

$$\forall i \in \mathbb{Z}, f(x_0^i) = P_4(x_0^i).$$

In particular, for every $i = 2m$ with $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $x_0^2 \in \mathbb{R}_+$ and we have

$$f(x_0^{2m}) = P_4(x_0^{2m}) = P_1(x_0^{2m}).$$

We conclude that $f = P_1$ on $x_0 \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{-1\}$, and, by continuity, we recover the equality on \mathbb{R} . f is indeed a polynomial on \mathbb{R} . ■

Theorem 9 (A characterization of complex polynomials by linear recurrences)

Let $f(z)$ be a complex function, continuous on \mathbb{C} . If f satisfies

$$\forall z_0 \in \mathbb{C}, \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}, f\left(z_0^{k+n+1}\right) + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(z_0) f\left(z_0^{k+i}\right) = 0, \quad (17)$$

then f is a polynomial of degree less than or equal to n .

Proof. From theorem (8) we know that f is equal to a polynomial P_0 on \mathbb{R} . Let's take $z_0 \notin \mathbb{R}$ and outside the unit circle. Because of the recurrence, f equals a polynomial P_1 on all integral powers

of z_0 . Since $|z_0| > 1$, the function $g(\alpha) = |z_0|^\alpha$ define a continuous isomorphism from \mathbb{R}_+ to $[1, +\infty[$. We define in a unique way on \mathbb{R}_+ the function $h(\alpha) = z_0^\alpha$ by posing $z_0 = \rho_0 e^{i\theta_0}$, $\theta_0 \in [0, 2\pi[$,

$$h(\alpha) = \rho_0^\alpha e^{i\alpha\theta_0}.$$

This single-value function define a continuous mapping from \mathbb{R}_+^* to a spiral curve C_{z_0} in \mathbb{C} . h is injective, since we have

$$\begin{aligned} h(\alpha) &= h(\beta) \\ \Rightarrow \rho_0^\alpha e^{i\alpha\theta_0} &= \rho_0^\beta e^{i\beta\theta_0} \\ \Rightarrow \rho_0^\alpha &= \rho_0^\beta \\ \Rightarrow \alpha &= \beta \end{aligned} \quad \text{by taking log.}$$

We have then a bijective mapping between \mathbb{R}_+^* and the image curve C_{z_0} . The continuity of h arises from the continuity of g and the complex exponential function. Coming back to f , we take $\alpha = \frac{1}{q}$, with $q \in \mathbb{N}^*$, and there is a unique polynomial P_2 equal to f on the integral powers of $z_0^{\frac{1}{q}}$. As before, for every integer $m \in \mathbb{N}^*$, we have

$$f\left(\left(z_0^{\frac{1}{q}}\right)^{mq}\right) = P_2\left(\left(z_0^{\frac{1}{q}}\right)^{mq}\right) = f(z_0^m) = P_1(z_0^m) = P_2(z_0^m).$$

P_1 and P_2 are equal on infinitely many points in \mathbb{C} , then they are equal everywhere. This proves that P_1 and f are also equal for every positive rational powers of z_0 . By continuity of h , the density of \mathbb{Q}_+^* in \mathbb{R}_+^* implies the density of the rational powers of z_0 in the image curve C_{z_0} . It follows, by continuity of f and P_1 , that they are equal on the continuous curve C_{z_0} . The spiral C_{z_0} has an infinite number of intersection points with \mathbb{R} , obtained for $h(\alpha_k)$ with $\alpha_k = \frac{2k\pi}{\theta_0}$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}^*$. These points are distinct by injectivity of h . Then P_1 and P_0 are equal on this infinite set of complexe points and therefore necessarily on \mathbb{C} . We deduce that f is equal to P_0 for every complexe z_0 outside the unit circle and on \mathbb{R} . By continuity we recover the unit circle. We can do the same type of reasoning for the complexe numbers strictly inside the unit cicle but zero, and we recover the equality of f and P_0 inside the unit circle and by continuity also in zero. f is ultimately a polynomial on \mathbb{C} . ■

To conclude this part, we can observe that, for a fixed z_0 , there is a bijection between the vectorial space of polynomials of degree less or equal to n and the vectorial space of the solutions of one linear recurrence. Because of the linearity, this is an isomorphism of vectorial spaces. As we shall see in the next section, this isomorphism realizes, in the complexe case, a transformation which contains the special situation of the Discrete Fourier transform, when we take a root of unity for z_0 .

4 A bridge between Discrete Fourier theory and polynomials

Theorem 10 (The discrete mean formula on the unit circle)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complexe) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any α , a primitive root of unity of order $k \geq n + 1$, we have

$$\sum_{s=1}^k P(\alpha^s) = kP(0). \quad (18)$$

We can reformulate this by saying that, for any polynomial, the mean value on the $k - th$ primitive roots of unity is its value in zero, provided that the degree of $P(x)$ is strictly less than k .

We obtain this theorem if we use a primitive root of unity of order $n+1$ in theorem (2). The coefficients of the recurrence relation are, up to an alternate change of signe, the symmetric functions of the roots of unity, the value 1 apart.

Proof. Let's recall that, since α is a primitive root of unity of order $n+1$, it generates all the roots. The roots of unity of order $n+1$ are the roots of

$$K(x) = x^{n+1} - 1 = \prod_{i=0}^n (x - \alpha^i).$$

We note $\sum_{i=0}^n x^i = Q(x)$. Using the factorization

$$K(x) = x^{n+1} - 1 = (x-1) \sum_{i=0}^n x^i = (x-1) Q(x),$$

we have by identification

$$Q(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n x^i = \prod_{i=1}^n (x - \alpha^i) = \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(\alpha) x^i,$$

and we conclude that, for $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$

$$(-1)^{n-i} {}_0\sigma_{n-i,n}(\alpha) = 1.$$

For any polynomial P of degree n or less and for $k=0$, the recurrence (8) take now the form

$$\sum_{i=0}^n P(\alpha^i) - \pi_n(\alpha) P(0) = 0.$$

We need to compute

$$\pi_n(\alpha) = \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - \alpha^i).$$

But we have $\prod_{i=1}^n (1 - \alpha^i) = Q(1) = n+1$ that lets us conclude.

We also have a direct proof of this result. We set $P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$ and by changing the order of summation

$$\sum_{s=1}^k P(\alpha^s) = \sum_{s=1}^k \sum_{i=0}^n a_i \alpha^{si} = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i \sum_{s=1}^k \alpha^{si}.$$

For $1 \leq i \leq n < k$, α^i is a root of $\sum_{s=0}^{k-1} x^s$, but from the cyclicity of the α^i , it is also a root of $\sum_{s=1}^k x^s$ which sums the same powers. For $i=0$, $\sum_{s=1}^k \alpha^{si} = k$ that let's conclude. ■

Example 10.1 Any polynomial of degree 2 satisfies

$$\sum_{s=0}^4 P(i^s) = 4P(0) \text{ and } \sum_{s=0}^3 P(j^s) = 3P(0).$$

where i denotes the imaginary unit and $j = e^{\frac{2i\pi}{3}}$.

For polynomials of degree two, the mean theorem is true for any regular polygon with three or more vertices and everywhere in the complex plane as we are going to see now.

Theorem 11 (The discrete mean formula for polynomials on any regular polygon)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any circle in \mathbb{C} , with center z_0 and radius $\rho > 0$, α a primitive root of unity of order $n + 1$, and an argument $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ we have

$$\sum_{m=0}^n P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) = (n + 1) P(z_0). \quad (19)$$

Proof. We use the fact that the polynomial $Q(z) = P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} z)$ has the same degree as $P(z)$ and thus satisfies the discrete mean theorem (10) for polynomials on the unit circle

$$\sum_{i=0}^n Q(\alpha^i) = (n + 1) Q(0),$$

where $Q(0) = P(z_0)$ and $Q(\alpha^i) = P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^i)$. ■

Example 11.1 For any regular octagon in \mathbb{C} with vertices z_i , for $i \in \{1, \dots, 8\}$, and for any polynomial P of degree less than or equal to 7, the mean of the value of P at the vertices equals the value at the center of the regular octagon. It's still true for any regular polygon with more vertices, any center and any radius.

We can produce another formula by using the homogeneous recurrence formula of theorem (1) on the roots of unity.

Theorem 12 (The null sum polynomial formula)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then, for any α , a primitive root of unity of order $n + 2$, we have

$$\sum_{s=0}^{n+1} P(\alpha^s) \alpha^s = 0. \quad (20)$$

Proof. We define the polynomial $Q(x) = xP(x)$ of degree $n + 1$ or less and we use the homogeneous recurrence formula (5) to this polynomial that vanishes in zero. We take $k = 0$ and $x_0 = \alpha$ and we obtain

$$P(\alpha^{n+1}) \alpha^{n+1} + \sum_{i=0}^n (-1)^{n-i+1} {}_0\sigma_{n-i+1, n+1}(\alpha) P(\alpha^i) \alpha^i = 0. \quad (21)$$

As in theorem(10), we still have, but for $i \in \{1, \dots, n + 1\}$ and α of order $n + 2$,

$$(-1)^{n-i+1} {}_0\sigma_{n-i+1, n+1}(\alpha) = 1.$$

From this, we deduce the simple formula

$$\sum_{s=0}^{n+1} P(\alpha^s) \alpha^s = 0.$$

We can provide another straightforward proof of this formula. We set $P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$ and by changing the order of summation

$$\sum_{s=0}^{n+1} P(\alpha^s) \alpha^s = \sum_{s=0}^{n+1} \sum_{i=0}^n a_i \alpha^{si} \alpha^s = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i \sum_{s=0}^{n+1} \alpha^{s(i+1)}.$$

Using that, for $1 \leq i \leq n + 1$, α^i is a root of $\sum_{s=0}^{n+1} x^s$, we obtain the result. ■

As before, we can again extend this formula to any regular polygon in \mathbb{C} .

Theorem 13 (The extended null sum polynomial formula)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any circle in \mathbb{C} , with center z_0 and radius $\rho > 0$, α a primitive root of unity of order $n + 2$, and an argument $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ we have

$$\sum_{s=0}^{n+1} P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^s) \alpha^s = 0. \quad (22)$$

As the proof proceeds the same way as in theorem (11), we don't provide it.

Theorem 14 (The discrete Cauchy formula on the unit circle)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then

1. for any α a primitive root of unity of order $n + 1$, we have

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!}. \quad (23)$$

2. for any α a primitive root of unity of order $p + 1 > n + 1$, we have

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, \frac{1}{p+1} \sum_{m=0}^p P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!} \quad (24)$$

but this time

$$\forall s \in \{n + 1, \dots, p - 1\}, \sum_{m=0}^p P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = 0 \quad (25)$$

Proof. If we take a look at the extended polynomial recurrences (12) with $k = 0$ and when $x_0 = \alpha$ a primitive root of unity of order $n + 1$, then we have, for any polynomial P of degree n and for each $s \in \{0, \dots, n\}$

$$P(\alpha^n) + \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-m} {}_s\sigma_{n-m,n}(\alpha) P(\alpha^m) = a_s \prod_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \neq s}}^{m=n} (\alpha^s - \alpha^m). \quad (26)$$

where a_s is the coefficient of degree s in the expanded form of P . The coefficients of the left member are the coefficients of the polynomial $Q(t)$ with zeros in α^k , $k \in \{0, \dots, s-1, s+1, \dots, n\}$. This polynomial can be expressed by

$$Q(t) = \frac{\prod_{m=0}^n (t - \alpha^m)}{t - \alpha^s} = \frac{t^{n+1} - 1}{t - \alpha^s}$$

Using a polynomial division, we have alternatively by reindexation

$$Q(t) = \sum_{m=0}^n t^{n-m} \alpha^{ms} = \sum_{m=0}^n t^m \alpha^{(n-m)s}.$$

Identifying by this formula the coefficients of the recurrence relation (26) and replacing them, we rewrite it like this

$$\sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{(n-m)s} = a_s \prod_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \neq s}}^{m=n} (\alpha^s - \alpha^m). \quad (27)$$

In the right member of (26), we observe that

$$\prod_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \neq s}}^{m=n} (\alpha^s - \alpha^m) = Q(\alpha^s) = \sum_{m=0}^n \alpha^{ms} \alpha^{(n-m)s} = \sum_{m=0}^n \alpha^{ns} = \alpha^{ns} (n+1). \quad (28)$$

Coming back to the left member of (27) we extract a factor in

$$\sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{(n-m)s} = \alpha^{ns} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-ms}. \quad (29)$$

Combining (28) and (29) and using $a_s = \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!}$, we reconstruct the attended formula (23) of the point (1).

For the point (2), P being a polynomial of degree $n < p$, we can use the extended polynomial recurrences (12) with the same conditions except for the degree p , that is

$$P(\alpha^p) + \sum_{m=0}^{p-1} (-1)^{p-m} {}_s\sigma_{p-m,p}(\alpha) P(\alpha^m) = a_s \prod_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \neq s}}^{m=p} (\alpha^s - \alpha^m). \quad (30)$$

The calculations are similar to the previous point, except for the limit of the sums and products where we replace n by p . The right member of (30) becomes

$$\prod_{\substack{m=0 \\ m \neq s}}^{m=p} (\alpha^s - \alpha^m) = Q(\alpha^s) = \sum_{m=0}^p \alpha^{ms} \alpha^{(p-m)s} = \sum_{m=0}^p \alpha^{ps} = \alpha^{ps} (p+1). \quad (31)$$

whereas the left member of (30) gives

$$\sum_{m=0}^p P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{(p-m)s} = \alpha^{ps} \sum_{m=0}^p P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-ms}. \quad (32)$$

We can see that the difference intervenes only with $a_s = \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!}$. Indeed, for P of degree n , $P^{(s)}(0) = 0$ as soon as $s \geq n + 1$, which cancels the right member in (30) and explains the formula (25) of the last point. ■

Theorem 15 (The discrete Cauchy's inequalities for polynomials)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any α a primitive root of unity of order $n + 2$ and any $s, s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, we have

$$|P^{(s)}(0)| \leq s! \max_{0 \leq m \leq n} |P(\alpha^m)|. \quad (33)$$

Proof. Starting from formula [], we can obtain an upper bound for the involved sum. From the equality,

$$\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!}$$

we extract

$$|P^{(s)}(0)| \leq \frac{s!}{n+1} \left| \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} \right|.$$

With $n + 1$ terms and $|\alpha^{-sm}| = 1$, we have

$$|P^{(s)}(0)| \leq s! \max_{0 \leq m \leq n} |P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm}| \leq s! \max_{0 \leq m \leq n} |P(\alpha^m)|.$$

■

Now we can interpret these formulas as a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). Let's recall the definition of the (DFT). Let α be a primitive root of the unity of order $n + 1$. For a vector $y = (y_0, \dots, y_n) \in \mathbb{C}^{n+1}$, the discrete Fourier Transform of y of order $n + 1$ is a vector $Y = (Y_0, \dots, Y_n) \in \mathbb{C}^{n+1}$ defined by

$$\text{for } s \in \{0, \dots, n\} \quad Y_s = \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n y_m \alpha^{-ms}. \quad (34)$$

We recognize exactly, in the formula (23), the (DFT) where the initial vector y is composed of the values of P on the roots of unity of order $n + 1$. The result Y is composed of the coefficients a_s of the polynomial. It is well known that it's a polynomial interpolation formula on the roots of unity of order $n + 1$, but we can understand now that it's a particular case of the linear recurrences for polynomials we have introduced and thus the (DFT) enters naturally in the theory of polynomials.

Theorem 16 (The shifted discrete Cauchy formulas on the unit circle.)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and α a primitive root of unity of order $n + 1$, we have

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{m+k}) \alpha^{-sm} = \alpha^{ks} \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!}. \quad (35)$$

Proof. This is literally the theorem (6) with any value for k and the same results provided in the previous theorem (14). To check consistency, we just rewrite the formula under the form

$$\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{m+k}) \alpha^{-s(m+k)} = \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!}. \quad (36)$$

When m describes $\{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, α^m goes through all the roots of unity and α^{m+k} does the same as in (1) with only a shift that doesn't affect the sum. ■

Let's go further, using the (DFT) to prove more results on the values of polynomials on any regular polygon. For this we state the following theorem.

Theorem 17 (The generalized discrete Cauchy formulas on any regular polygon)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then for any circle in \mathbb{C} , with center z_0 and radius $\rho > 0$ and an argument $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ we have

1. for any α a primitive root of unity of order $n + 1$, we have

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, \quad \frac{1}{(n+1)\rho^s e^{is\theta}} \sum_{m=0}^n P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = \frac{P^{(s)}(z_0)}{s!}. \quad (37)$$

2. for any α a primitive root of unity of order $p \geq n + 1$, we have again

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, \quad \frac{1}{(p+1)\rho^s e^{is\theta}} \sum_{m=0}^p P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = \frac{P^{(s)}(z_0)}{s!} \quad (38)$$

but this time

$$\forall s \in \{n+1, \dots, p-1\}, \quad \sum_{m=0}^p P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = 0 \quad (39)$$

Proof. As we have done before, we use the polynomial $Q(z) = P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} z)$ that has the same degree as $P(z)$ and thus satisfy the discrete Cauchy theorem for polynomials on the unit circle. For the case of roots of unity of order $n + 1$, we have so

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}, \quad \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n Q(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} = \frac{Q^{(s)}(0)}{s!}. \quad (40)$$

The linear function $T(z) = z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} z$ has a constant derivative $e^{i\theta}$ that multiply each step of derivation. We obtain successively

$$Q^{(s)}(0) = (P(T(z)))^{(s)}(0) = P^{(s)}(T(z))(0) (\rho e^{i\theta})^s = P^{(s)}(z_0) (\rho e^{i\theta})^s$$

Replacing in (40) we get the announced result. The other formulas are constructed absolutely similarly. ■

As with the case of the discrete Cauchy's inequalities, we can deduce more general similar inequalities for the modulus of the derivatives of a polynomial in any point $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}$.

Theorem 18 (The generalized discrete Cauchy's inequalities for polynomials)

Let $P(x)$ be a real (complex) polynomial of degree less than or equal to n , $n \in \mathbb{N}$. For any circle in \mathbb{C} , with center z_0 and radius $\rho > 0$ and an argument $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ and α a primitive root of unity of order $p \geq n + 1$ and any $s, s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, we have

$$|P^{(s)}(z_0)| \leq \frac{s!}{\rho^s} \max_{0 \leq m \leq n} |P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m)|. \quad (41)$$

Proof. From the equality [], we extract

$$P^{(s)}(z_0) = \frac{s!}{(p+1)\rho^s e^{is\theta}} \sum_{m=0}^p P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm}$$

and then, with $|\alpha^{-sm}| = |e^{is\theta}| = 1$ and $p + 1$ terms in the sum,

$$|P^{(s)}(z_0)| \leq \frac{s!}{\rho^s} \max_{0 \leq m \leq n} \left| P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} \right| \leq \frac{s!}{\rho^s} \max_{0 \leq m \leq n} \left| P(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta} \alpha^m) \right|$$

■

It remains to treat the case where we evaluate a polynomial P of degree n on a regular polygon with less vertices than $n + 1$.

Theorem 19 (The Discrete Fourier Transform for polynomials) Let P be a polynomial of degree n whose expanded form is $P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k \leq n$. If α is a primitive root of unity of order k then if q is the quotient of the euclidean division of n by k

$$\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} P(\alpha^i) = \sum_{i=0}^q a_{ik} \quad (42)$$

Proof. In foreplay, we introduces two usefull known results. The (DFT) has a kind property related to cyclic convolution. The result of the cyclic convolution of two vectors $x = (x_i)_{0 \leq i \leq n-1}$ and $y = (y_i)_{0 \leq i \leq n-1}$ in \mathbb{C}^n is a vector $z = (z_i)_{0 \leq i \leq n-1}$ defined by

$$\forall k \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\} \quad z_k = \sum_{q=0}^{n-1} x_q y_{(k-q) \pmod{n}} \quad (43)$$

where $(k-q) \pmod{n}$ is the representative integer of $(k-q)$ in $\{0, \dots, n-1\}$ in arithmetic modulo n . If we note the result $z = x * y$ and X, Y and Z the respective (DFT) of x, y and z , then we have

$$\forall k \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\} \quad Z_k = nX_k Y_k \quad (44)$$

and conversely, if $z = x y$, that is to say, $\forall k \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$, $z_k = x_k y_k$, then

$$\forall k \in \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\} \quad Z_k = \sum_{q=0}^{n-1} X_q Y_{(k-q) \pmod{n}} = X * Y. \quad (45)$$

In other words, the (DFT) converts a cyclic convolution into a product term by term, up to a constant factor and conversely, convert a product term by term into a cyclic convolution. The second standard result we use without proof is that if α is a primitive root of unity of order $n = kp$, where k and p are integers, then α^p is a primitive root of unity of order k . Now, let's take a polynomial of degree n , and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$k \leq n \text{ and } n = kq + r \text{ with } r < k \quad (46)$$

We note $N = (q+1)k$ and, from above, we have $N \geq n+1$. With N we have a sufficiently large value to apply our previous result (40). Let α be a primitive root of unity of order N . $N = k(q+1)$ ensures that $\beta = \alpha^{q+1}$ is a primitive root of unity of order k . Now we define the polynomial Q_k , of degree strictly less than N , by its values on the roots of unity of order N

$$Q_k(\alpha^i) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = (q+1)j \text{ with } j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

This polynomial is expressly built to select in the set of values $P(\alpha^i)$ the only ones that are necessary for us, the $P(\beta^j) = P(\alpha^{(q+1)j})$. Thus we can write

$$\sum_{i=0}^{k-1} P(\beta^i) = \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} P(\alpha^{(q+1)i}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P(\alpha^i) Q_k(\alpha^i). \quad (48)$$

The polynomial $Q_k(x)$ has for expanded form

$$Q_k(x) = \frac{1}{q+1} \sum_{i=0}^q x^{ik}. \quad (49)$$

Indeed, for $s = j(q+1)$, $j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$, α^s is a k -th root of unity and

$$\frac{1}{q+1} \sum_{i=0}^q \left(\alpha^{j(q+1)} \right)^{ik} = \frac{1}{q+1} \sum_{i=0}^q \left(\alpha^{k(q+1)} \right)^{ij} = 1 = Q_k(\alpha^s) \quad (50)$$

Otherwise, for $s \neq j(q+1)$, $j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$, α^s is not a k -th root of unity

$$\frac{1}{q+1} \sum_{i=0}^q (\alpha^s)^{ik} = \frac{1}{q+1} \frac{\alpha^{sk(q+1)} - 1}{\alpha^{sk} - 1} = 0 = Q_k(\alpha^s) \quad (51)$$

We recognize in (48), up to a constant factor $\frac{1}{N}$, the DFT of length N of the product of polynomials P and Q_k , evaluated on the first component. This means we have taken $s = 0$ in (40). The result is then the convolution of their DFT. The DFT is the interpolation process on roots of unity, and for an order $N \geq n+1$ we have seen that we recover the coefficients of the polynomial, the goal of the interpolation. The DFT of P is the vector $X = (a_0, \dots, a_n, 0, \dots, 0)$ with zeros to complete the coefficients up to $N-1$, to respect the order of our DFT. The DFT of Q is the vector $Y = (1, 0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots)$ with repeated 1 at indexes ik , $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, q\}$. To conclude, we just need to compute

$$(X * Y)_0 = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} a_{ik}. \quad (52)$$

Let's remark that $Y_{-i} = Y_{N-i}$ and $N-i = k(q+1) - i = ks$ with $s \in \{0, 1, \dots, q\}$ if and only if $i = k(q+1-s)$, $q+1-s \in \{0, 1, \dots, q+1\}$. That means that $Y_{N-i} = 1$ if and only if i is a multiple of k , otherwise $Y_{N-i} = 0$. Ultimately, $Y_{N-i} = Y_i$ for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, N-1\}$ and

$$(X * Y)_0 = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} X_i Y_i = \sum_{i=0}^q X_{ik} = \sum_{i=0}^q a_{ik}. \quad (53)$$

■

As a consequence, if we take $a_{ik} = 1$ in (53), we remark that we obtain the quotient q as the result of the mean, but let's leave that aside. With a little step forward we can get a more general formula. In the same way, if we come back to the generalized discrete Cauchy formula (1), we may wonder what the formula gives when the order of the primitive root of unity is less than or equal to the degree of the polynomial. This only introduces a supplementary factor α^{-si} in the sum. If we join it with the polynomial $Q_k(x)$ we get a new polynomial $H_k(x) = Q_k(x)x^{-s+k}$ evaluated on the same α^i . To achieve the same reasoning, we just need to understand its DFT. With multiplication by x^{-s+k} , the coefficients of the polynomial don't change their values but they are each displaced, going backward with the same decrease of s in the indexes. One might wonder why we add k . We have the hypothesis that s is less than or equal to n in (41), in a similar way we have here that s is less than or equal to k and this ensures that $-s+k \geq 0$ and $H_k(x)$ is then a polynomial. From the point of view of roots of unity of order k , it doesn't change the values because $\alpha^k = 1$. Thus with the same clockwise shift for each coefficient of $Q_k(x)$ we obtain the same shift but counterclockwise in the convolution formula with the DFT of $H_k(x)$. Thus we get the concentration of the coefficients one's on the indexes $ik+s$. We can now formulate this result.

Theorem 20 (The shifted DFT for polynomials)

Let P be a polynomial of degree n whose expanded form is $P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$ and $k \in \mathbb{N}$ with $k \leq n$. If α is a primitive root of unity of order k and if q is the quotient of the euclidean division of n by k , then

$$\forall s \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\} \quad \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} P(\alpha^i) \alpha^{-is} = \sum_{i=0}^q a_{ik+s}. \quad (54)$$

So far, we have been focused on the link of polynomial recurrent relations with DFT and its use to completely solve the computation of the mean of a polynomial on regular polygons. If we mentioned the known link between DFT and interpolation on the roots of unity, we extend now the link between Lagrange interpolation and polynomial linear recurrences. This will give another

approach to the linear recurrences satisfied by polynomials. Let's briefly recall the Lagrange polynomial interpolation and its formulation. The Lagrange interpolation for a set of n nodes with distinct abscissa $x_i, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, corresponds to the construction of an orthonormal basis of the vectorial space of polynomials of degree less or equal to n , with respect to the scalar product defined by

$$\forall P, Q \in \mathbb{R}(x) \quad \langle P, Q \rangle = \sum_{i=0}^n P(x_i)Q(x_i). \quad (55)$$

If we get a family of polynomials $L_i(x)$, such that

$$\forall i, j \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\} \quad \langle L_i, L_j \rangle = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } i = j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (56)$$

the solution of finding a polynomial, whose values at the x_i 's are respectively $y_i, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, is given by

$$\forall j \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\} \quad L_j(x) = \frac{\prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x - x_i)}{\prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_j - x_i)} \quad (57)$$

We analyse now the particular cases of nodes in geometric progression, $x_i = x_0^i, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$. We take the same precautions as in the polynomial recurrences, assuming that the x_i 's are distinct.

Theorem 21 (The Lagrange interpolation and linear recurrences)

Let, for any fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $L_i^k(x), i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, be the Lagrange polynomials of degree n at the nodes of distinct abscissa $x_i = x_0^{i+k}, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$. We have

1. $L_i^k(x_0^{i+k})$ doesn't depend on k

$$\forall k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad L_i^k(x_0^{n+k+1}) = L_i^0(x_0^{n+1}) \quad (58)$$

2. for any polynomial P of degree less than or equal to n , we have the linear polynomial recurrent relations

$$P(x_0^{n+k+1}) = \sum_{i=0}^n P(x_0^{k+i}) L_i^0(x_0^{n+1}) \quad (59)$$

3. for $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, we can express a link with symmetric functions and Lagrange polynomials as

$$L_i^0(x_0^{n+1}) = (-1)^{n-i} \sigma_{n-i+1, n+1}(x_0). \quad (60)$$

Proof. For a given $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and for any $j \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, the Lagrange polynomial L_j^k at the distinct abscissa $x_i = x_0^{i+k}, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, evaluated in x_0^{n+k+1} is

$$\forall j \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\} \quad L_j^k(x_0^{n+k+1}) = \frac{\prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_0^{n+k+1} - x_0^{i+k})}{\prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_0^{j+k} - x_0^{i+k})}. \quad (61)$$

We have x_0^k in factor everywhere such that

$$\forall j \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\} \quad L_j^k(x_0^{n+k+1}) = \frac{x_0^k \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_0^{n+1} - x_0^i)}{x_0^k \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^n (x_0^j - x_0^i)} = L_j^0(x_0^{n+1}). \quad (62)$$

For the point (2), we use the fact that P has a unique decomposition in the basis of Lagrange polynomials at $x_i = x_0^{i+k}$, $i \in \{0, 1, \dots, n\}$, given by

$$P(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n P(x_0^{k+i}) L_i^k(x). \quad (63)$$

Evaluated in x_0^{n+k+1} and using the point(2), this formula becomes

$$P(x_0^{n+k+1}) = \sum_{i=0}^n P(x_0^{k+i}) L_i^k(x_0^{n+k+1}) = \sum_{i=0}^n P(x_0^{k+i}) L_i^0(x_0^{n+1}). \quad (64)$$

This clearly provides a linear recurrence for the values $P(x_0^i)$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$. The last point is a direct consequence of the unicity of the recurrence satisfied by the sequence $P(x_0^i)$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$, and the coefficients we met in the recurrence given by (10). The power $(-1)^{n-i}$ is only due to the change of side in the equalities. ■

The previous result corroborates the fact that we were using Lagrange interpolation on successive powers of the same number when we were building the characteristic polynomial from this choice of roots. But it was not straightforward to anticipate that the Lagrange functions coefficients could be constant for the next powers and building so a recurrent relation. Now we can answer to another question. When we have a recurrence relation, we can always express the successive terms of the recurrence as a linear combination of the starting values used to initialize the recurrence, provided that the term is not in these starting values. The question that arises for a polynomial of degree n is then, since $P(x_0^i)$ is a linear recurrent sequence that starts from the initialization values $\{P(1), P(x_0), \dots, P(x_0^n)\}$, how can we express $P(x_0^{n+k+1})$ with a linear combination of the initialization values. The Lagrange decomposition gives immediately the answer.

$$P(x_0^{n+k+1}) = \sum_{i=0}^n P(x_0^i) L_i^0(x_0^{n+k+1}). \quad (65)$$

It's important to notice that the linear recurrence relations are not interpolation constraints. When we interpolate, we affect independantly values for the function at specified nodes. These are ponctual constraints. When we use a polynomial linear recurrence on powers, we are just imposing a relation satisfied by any polynomial with degree less than a fixed integer. The relations link the successive values at specified nodes and are no more ponctual constraints.

5 Matrix formulation

We take advantage of the synthetic form of the polynomial linear recurrences offered by the Lagrange polynomials to briefly present the matrix formulation of these recurrences. For a polynomial of degree n and distinct abscissa $x_i = x_0^i$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$, we can write the recurrence relation (10) or (59) in the matrix form

$$\begin{pmatrix} P(1) & P(x_0) & \dots & P(x_0^n) \\ P(x_0) & P(x_0^2) & \dots & P(x_0^{n+1}) \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ P(x_0^n) & P(x_0^{n+1}) & \dots & P(x_0^{2n}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} L_0(x_0^{n+1}) \\ L_1(x_0^{n+1}) \\ \vdots \\ L_n(x_0^{n+1}) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P(x_0^{n+1}) \\ P(x_0^{n+2}) \\ \vdots \\ P(x_0^{2n+1}) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (66)$$

The matrix is a Hankel matrix that we may encounter in many situations [ref]. The study of their determinants is a tool for the detection of recurrences [ref], hence we can use this property to detect the degree of a polynomial only known by its values.

Theorem 22 *For any real (complex) polynomial of degree n , we have*

$$\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^*(\mathbb{C}^*), \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \left| \begin{array}{cccc} P(x_0^k) & P(x_0^{k+1}) & \dots & P(x_0^{k+n+1}) \\ P(x_0^{k+1}) & P(x_0^{k+2}) & \dots & P(x_0^{k+n+2}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P(x_0^{k+n+1}) & P(x_0^{k+n+2}) & \dots & P(x_0^{k+2n+2}) \end{array} \right| = 0 \quad (67)$$

Proof. $\forall x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^*(\mathbb{C}^*)$, the recurrence relations can be interpreted in term of orthogonality of vectors. If we note

$$p_{n,k} = (P(x_0^k), P(x_0^{k+1}), \dots, P(x_0^{k+n+1}))$$

and

$$s_n = (-L_0(x_0^{n+1}), -L_1(x_0^{n+1}), \dots, -L_n(x_0^{n+1}), 1),$$

then, the Lagrange recurrence equation (59) says exactly that, for a fixed n and for all k , the $p_{n,k}$, living in a $n+1$ dimensional space, are all orthogonal to the same vector s_n . In this case, if we take $n+1$ values of k , the $n+1$ associated vectors $p_{n,k}$ are in the orthogonal of s_n , which is of dimension n . $n+1$ vectors in a vectorial space of dimension n are not independent and their determinant is zero. ■

We can dig deeper into the matrix interpretation of theorem (17). The fact, that the coefficients of the linear combination in formula (26) don't depend on k , allows us to view it as property of eigenvectors.

Theorem 23 *For any real (complex) polynomial of degree n , for any root of unity α of order $n+1$ and for all k in \mathbb{N} , the matrices*

$$M_k(\alpha) = \begin{pmatrix} P(\alpha^k) & P(\alpha^{k+1}) & \dots & P(\alpha^{k+n}) \\ P(\alpha^{k+1}) & P(\alpha^{k+2}) & \dots & P(\alpha^{k+n+1}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ P(\alpha^{k+n}) & P(\alpha^{k+n+1}) & \dots & P(\alpha^{k+2n}) \end{pmatrix} \quad (68)$$

have for eigenvectors

$$e_s^+(\alpha) = \left(\alpha^{-ks} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-sn} \end{pmatrix} + \left(\alpha^{ks} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{sn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (69)$$

and

$$e_s^-(\alpha) = \left(\alpha^{-ks} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-sn} \end{pmatrix} - \left(\alpha^{ks} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{sn} \end{pmatrix} \quad (70)$$

with respective eigenvalues

$$v_s^+ = (n+1) \left(\sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad v_s^- = -v_s^+, \quad (71)$$

when s describes the set $\{0, \dots, n\}$.

Proof. We begin by collecting informations on $M_k^2(\alpha)$. We note, as before, $a_k = \frac{P^{(k)}(0)}{k!}$, the coefficients of the polynomial P . The use of the shifted discrete Cauchy theorem (16) and the introduction of a factor α^{si} to make it appear, gives us the image of a simple vector

$$\begin{pmatrix} P(\alpha^k) & P(\alpha^{k+1}) & \dots & P(\alpha^{k+n}) \\ P(\alpha^{k+1}) & P(\alpha^{k+2}) & \dots & P(\alpha^{k+n+1}) \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ P(\alpha^{k+n}) & P(\alpha^{k+n+1}) & \dots & P(\alpha^{k+2n}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-sn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m}) \alpha^{-sm} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+i}) \alpha^{-sm} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+n}) \alpha^{-sm} \end{pmatrix} \quad (72)$$

$$= (n+1) \alpha^{sk} a_s \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{sn} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (73)$$

Using the relationship (36),

$$\sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m}) \alpha^{-sm} = (n+1) \alpha^{sk} a_s, \quad (74)$$

we have simplified each row with

$$\alpha^{si} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+i}) \alpha^{-sm-si} = \alpha^{si} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+i}) \alpha^{-s(m+i)} = \alpha^{si} (n+1) \alpha^{sk} a_s. \quad (75)$$

For $s = 0$, this gives immediatly an eigenvector $v_0 = (1, \dots, 1)^T$, with eigenvalue $(n+1)a_0$. Now, for $s \neq 0$, we apply $M_k(\alpha)$ one more time.

$$M_k(\alpha) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{sn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m}) \alpha^{sm} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+i}) \alpha^{sm} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+n}) \alpha^{sm} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (76)$$

We can convert α^{sm} to accommodate it to theorem (16) while writing $\alpha^s = \alpha^{-(n+1-s)}$.

$$M_k(\alpha) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{sn} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m}) \alpha^{-(n+1-s)m} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+i}) \alpha^{-(n+1-s)m} \\ \vdots \\ \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+n}) \alpha^{-(n+1-s)m} \end{pmatrix} = (n+1) \alpha^{(n+1-s)k} a_{n+1-s} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{(n+1-s)i} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{(n+1-s)n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (77)$$

This has been similarly simplified with

$$\alpha^{(n+1-s)i} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m+i}) \alpha^{-(n+1-s)(m+i)} = \alpha^{(n+1-s)i} (n+1) \alpha^{(n+1-s)k} a_{n+1-s} \quad (78)$$

and we obtain

$$M_k(\alpha) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{sn} \end{pmatrix} = (n+1) \alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-sn} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (79)$$

Combining (79) and (72), we obtain an eigenvector and an eigenvalue of $M_k^2(\alpha)$, for each value of s with

$$M_k^2(\alpha) \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-sn} \end{pmatrix} = (n+1)^2 a_s a_{n+1-s} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-si} \\ \vdots \\ \alpha^{-sn} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (80)$$

We deduce from this the eigenvalues of $M_k(\alpha)$. Indeed, the eigenvalues of $M_k(\alpha)$ are the square roots of the eigenvalues of $M_k^2(\alpha)$. Coming back to (79) and (72), we see that $M_k(\alpha)$ interchanges the two vectors defined by $w_s^+(\alpha) = (1, \dots, \alpha^{si}, \dots, \alpha^{sn})$ and $w_s^-(\alpha) = (1, \dots, \alpha^{-si}, \dots, \alpha^{-sn})$. We can search an eigenvector of $M_k(\alpha)$ as a linear combination of these two vectors. We set $w_s = \gamma w_s^+(\alpha) + \beta w_s^-(\alpha)$ and we impose that it is an eigenvector of $M_k(\alpha)$ with some eigenvalue λ .

$$\begin{aligned} M_k(\alpha) w_s &= \lambda w_s \\ \gamma w_s^-(\alpha) (n+1) \alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s} + \beta w_s^+(\alpha) (n+1) \alpha^{sk} a_s &= \lambda \gamma w_s^+(\alpha) + \lambda \beta w_s^-(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

From the independance of the two vectors $v_s^+(\alpha)$ and $v_s^-(\alpha)$, we deduce that

$$\begin{cases} \gamma (n+1) \alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s} = \lambda \beta \\ \beta (n+1) \alpha^{sk} a_s = \lambda \gamma \end{cases} \quad (81)$$

By substitution, we have first that $\lambda^2 = (n+1)^2 a_s a_{n+1-s}$ and then

$$\gamma \alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s} = \pm \sqrt{a_s a_{n+1-s}} \beta. \quad (82)$$

If we choose $\beta = (\alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s})^{\frac{1}{2}}$, then we must have $\gamma = \pm (\alpha^{sk} a_s)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. We can now reconstitute the eigenvectors,

$$w_s = \gamma w_s^+(\alpha) + \beta w_s^-(\alpha) = \pm \left(\alpha^{sk} a_s \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} w_s^+(\alpha) + \left(\alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} w_s^-(\alpha) \quad (83)$$

or alternatively, using the values of P on the roots of unity and a reindexation, we obtain

$$\beta = \left(\alpha^{-sk} a_{n+1-s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^{k+m}) \alpha^{-(n+1-s)m} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{1}{n+1} \alpha^{-ks} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\gamma = \pm \left(\alpha^{sk} a_s \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \pm \left(\frac{1}{n+1} \alpha^{ks} \sum_{m=0}^n P(\alpha^m) \alpha^{-sm} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

The eigen vectors are defined to within a multiplicative constant. We can then omit the common factor $\frac{1}{n+1}$ in γ and β to find the formula given in the statement. The case $\alpha = 0$ is also covered by this formula.

■

To complete all the previous algebraic aspects, we can show that the linear recurrences on powers for polynomials are true in more general contexts.

Theorem 24 *Let \mathbb{A} be a commutative ring and $a_0 \in \mathbb{A}$. If we build, with $c_i \in \mathbb{A}$ for $i = \{0, \dots, n\}$, a linear combination $C(a_0) = \sum_{i=0}^n c_i a_0^i$ of n successive powers of the element a_0 , then we have for $k \in \mathbb{N}$*

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n+1} C(a_0^{i+k}) (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n-i+1, n+1}(a_0) = 0 \quad (84)$$

where $\sigma_{n-i+1, n+1}(a_0)$ are the symmetric functions as defined earlier and -1 designates the opposite of the neutral element of the multiplication in \mathbb{A} .

Proof. The expressions $\sigma_{n-i+1, n+1}(a_0)$ are perfectly defined in \mathbb{A} as linear combinations of powers of x_0 and have integer coefficients. Indeed, they are coming from multivariate elementary symmetric functions who have only integer coefficients. They are also the coefficients of the formal expansion of the polynomial $P(t) = \prod_{i=0}^n (t - x_0^i)$ and as such $P(x_0^i) = 0$ for $i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$. Now, we replace the $C(a_0^{i+k})$ by their expressions in

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} C(a_0^{i+k}) (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(a_0) &= \sum_{i=0}^{n+1} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n c_j (x_0^k)^j \right) (-1)^{n-i} \sigma_{n-i, n}(a_0) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n c_i \sum_{j=0}^{n+1} (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(a_0) (x_0^k)^i \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n c_i \sum_{j=0}^{n+1} (-1)^{n+1-i} \sigma_{n+1-i, n+1}(a_0) (x_0^i)^k \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n c_i P(x_0^i) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

■

For example, we can use such recurrences in \mathbb{Z} or $\mathbb{Z}[\mathbb{X}]$, \mathbb{Z}_p , $\mathbb{Z}_p[X]$. Let's remark that the formula is evenly true for a polynomial of a matrix M with coefficients in a commutative ring, as we can still build $P(t) = \prod_{i=0}^n (t - M^i)$ such that $P(M^i) = 0$ for $i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$.

6 A bridge to analytical functions

At first glance, computing polynomials on regular polygons seems quite a strange idea, but analytical functions are the limits of their partial sums which are all polynomials. We can expect that properties that are universal and uniformly shared by these partial sums can be transmitted to their limit. We begin with the well known theorem for analytical functions that said their integral path are null on closed outline inside the domain of analyticity. Let's derive a proof coming from the recurrence relations for polynomials.

Theorem 25 Let $f(z)$ be an analytic function on a domain D . Then, for any circle $C_{z_0, \rho} \subset D$, centered in z_0 and of radius ρ , the property

$$\int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz = 0 \quad (85)$$

is an asymptotic consequence of the null sum polynomial formula.

Proof. As an analytical function on D , f has a development in a serie in z_0 that is uniformly convergent in $C_{z_0, \rho}$, and fo any z on $C_{z_0, \rho}$

$$f(z) = \sum_{i=0}^{+\infty} c_i z^i. \quad (86)$$

The analyticity of f ensures that the partial sums $P_k(z) = \sum_{i=0}^k c_i z^i$ are uniformly converging to $f(z)$ on the circle $C_{z_0, \rho}$. This allows us to write, for any $\epsilon_1 \in \mathbb{R}_+^*$

$$\exists N_{\epsilon_1} \text{ such that, } \forall N > N_{\epsilon_1} \text{ and } \forall z \in C_{z_0, \rho}, \quad |f(z) - P_N(z)| < \epsilon_1. \quad (87)$$

Moreover, the integral on the circle is defined by

$$\int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz = \int_0^{2\pi} f(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta}) \rho i e^{i\theta} d\theta \quad (88)$$

and, as for any continuous function, can be approached by a sum that discretized the integral on regularly spaced points on the circle. On the circle $C_{z_0, \rho}$, we may use the points $z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^i$, with α_k^i a primitive root of unity of order k . We hold the integral as the limit of the discret sums

$$\int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz = \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \quad (89)$$

and thus

$$\exists N_{\epsilon_2} \text{ such that, } \forall k > N_{\epsilon_2}, \quad \left| \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz - \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \right| < \epsilon_2. \quad (90)$$

We can now apply to our particular points of discretization

$$\forall N > N_{\epsilon_1}, \forall j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\} \quad \left| f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) - P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \right| < \epsilon_1. \quad (91)$$

By summation of k similar inequalities, we have successively, with $|\alpha_k^i| = 1$,

$$\forall N > N_{\epsilon_1}, \quad \left| \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j - \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \right| < k \rho \epsilon_1 \quad (92)$$

$$\forall N > N_{\epsilon_1}, \quad \left| \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j - \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \right| < 2\pi \rho \epsilon_1. \quad (93)$$

If we combine (93) and (90) we can majorize

$$\forall k > N_{\epsilon_2} \text{ and } N > N_{\epsilon_1},$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz - \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \right| < \left| \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz - \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \right| \\ & + \left| \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j - \frac{2i\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \rho \alpha_k^j \right| < \epsilon_2 + 2\pi \rho \epsilon_1. \quad (94) \end{aligned}$$

Now we can choose k the number of roots of unity in such a way that we can use our theorem (13). It is sufficient to have $k > N$ to ensure that the order of the primitive root α_k is greater than the degree N of P_N . We can fix $\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_1$, then $N > N_{\epsilon_1}$ and next $k > N$ to both satisfy the inequality and the condition relative to the order of the primitive root. In these cases we can use (22) which says that

$$\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^j = 0 \quad (95)$$

and we get

$$\left| \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} f(z) dz \right| < \epsilon_1 + 2\pi \rho \epsilon_1 \quad (96)$$

for any choice of ϵ_1 . This allows us to conclude. ■

The similarities between the discrete Cauchy formula for polynomials and the Cauchy properties for analytical functions invites us to explore more new proofs of these results to clearly emerge that, in essence, Cauchy theorems are asymptotic properties coming from their discrete counterpart for polynomials.

Theorem 26 *Let $f(z)$ be an analytic function on a domain D . Then, for any circle $C_{z_0, \rho} \subset D$, centered in z_0 and of radius ρ , and for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the formula*

$$\frac{n!}{2\pi i} \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} \frac{f(z)}{(z - z_0)^{n+1}} dz = f^{(n)}(z_0), \quad (97)$$

is an asymptotic consequence of the discrete Cauchy formula for polynomials.

Proof. We use the same process as in the previous theorem. We need to rewrite the integral (97) accordingly to the circular path $z = z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta}$ like this

$$\frac{n!}{2\pi i} \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} \frac{f(z)}{(z - z_0)^{n+1}} dz = \frac{n!}{2\pi \rho^n} \int_0^{2\pi} f(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta}) e^{-ni\theta} d\theta. \quad (98)$$

The next step that leads to modify formula is the discrete sum to approach the integral, as in (89). We keep unchanged the range of discretization, $z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j$, with α_k^j a primitive root of unity of order k . We just modify the function in the discrete sum and that becomes

$$\int_0^{2\pi} f(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta}) e^{-ni\theta} d\theta = \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{2\pi}{k} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} \quad (99)$$

$$\frac{n!}{2\pi \rho^n} \int_0^{2\pi} f(z_0 + \rho e^{i\theta}) e^{-ni\theta} d\theta = \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{n!}{k \rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn}. \quad (100)$$

As we have done before in (90), for any $\epsilon_2 \in \mathbb{R}_+^*$, we bring out that

$$\exists N_{\epsilon_2} \text{ such that, } \forall k > N_{\epsilon_2}, \quad \left| \frac{n!}{2\pi i} \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} \frac{f(z)}{(z - z_0)^{n+1}} dz - \frac{n!}{k \rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} \right| < \epsilon_2. \quad (101)$$

The step, where f is approached by polynomials, must be adapted accordingly. From the common approximation (87) we build the one we need. We have directly from

$$\forall N > N_{\epsilon_1}, \forall j \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\} \quad \left| f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) - P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \right| < \epsilon_1, \quad (102)$$

the inequality which control the error of the uniform polynomial approximation

$$\forall N > N_{\epsilon_1}, \quad \left| \frac{n!}{k \rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} - \frac{n!}{k \rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho \alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} \right| < \frac{n!}{\rho^n} \epsilon_1. \quad (103)$$

n and ρ being fixed we can still keep the bound as small as we want with a sufficiently large choice of N . The last step is to choose k sufficiently large to keep $k > N$, such that we can apply the generalized discrete Cauchy formula of theorem (17). With the choices of $\theta = 0$ and α_k the primitive root of unity of order k , that says that

$$\forall n \in \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}, \quad \frac{1}{k\rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} P_N(z_0 + \rho\alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} = \frac{P_N^{(n)}(z_0)}{n!}. \quad (104)$$

This formula is true as soon as k , the order of the root of unity, is strictly greater than the degree N of the polynomial and in these cases

$$\forall N > N_{\epsilon_1} \text{ and any } k > N, \quad \left| \frac{n!}{k\rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho\alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} - P_N^{(n)}(z_0) \right| < \frac{n!}{\rho^n} \epsilon_1. \quad (105)$$

Taking into account the equation (101) we obtain by gathering the two inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{n!}{2\pi i} \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} \frac{f(z)}{(z-z_0)^{n+1}} dz - f^{(n)}(z_0) \right| &< \left| \frac{n!}{k\rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho\alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} - P_N^{(n)}(z_0) \right| \\ &+ \left| \frac{n!}{2\pi i} \int_{C_{z_0, \rho}} \frac{f(z)}{(z-z_0)^{n+1}} dz - \frac{n!}{k\rho^n} \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} f(z_0 + \rho\alpha_k^j) \alpha_k^{-jn} \right| < \frac{n!}{\rho^n} \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2. \end{aligned}$$

Since for any choice of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 we can provide N and k to achieve this inequality, we conclude that the left member, constant for any chosen n and z_0 , is null.

■

We can ask ourselves if other well known properties related to analytical functions have their sibling in the world of polynomials. We have used so far, asymptotic reasoning to obtain, by this way, well known results for analytical functions. Reversing the process, we can also use discretization principle to get new formulas for polynomials from formulas satisfied by analytical functions.

Looking at the theorem (22), with $n = 2$, we can write for any constant polynomial $P(z)$ that

$$P(z+h) \times 1 + P(z+h \times (-1)) \times (-1) = 0,$$

for any $h \in \mathbb{C}$ and any $z \in \mathbb{C}$. Expressed in language of derivatives, we have

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{P(z+h) - P(z-h)}{h} = P'(z) = 0.$$

This invites us to ask two questions intimately linked. Can we generalize the interpretation of the theorem (22) as a derivative formula and could we have a reciprocal for theorem (22) as the Morera theorem for analytical functions. Indeed, the Morera theorem says that, if a complex continuous function satisfies the null integral property on any circle then it is an analytical function. The discrete counterpart of this theorem is then, if a continuous function satisfies the extended null sum theorem (22) then the function is a polynomial.

Theorem 27 (The symmetric definitions of complex derivatives) *For any analytical function f on an open set U in the complex plane, and any α primitive root of unity of order n , we have*

$$\forall z \in U, \quad \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} f(z+h\alpha^k) \alpha^k}{nh^{n-1}} = \frac{f^{(n-1)}(z)}{(n-1)!}. \quad (106)$$

Proof. Let f be an analytical function on an open set U in the complex plane. f admits, in any $z \in U$, a power series expansion which is convergent inside a disc with non null radius ρ_z .

$$\forall z_0 \in U, \exists \rho_{z_0} \in \mathbb{R}_+^*, \text{ such that } |z - z_0| < \rho_{z_0} \Rightarrow f(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} a_k (z - z_0)^k.$$

Let's take $z_0 \in U$, α a primitive root of unity of order n and $h \in \mathbb{C}$, with $0 < |h| < \rho_{z_0}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} f(z_0 + h\alpha^s) \alpha^s &= \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} a_k (h\alpha^s)^k \alpha^s \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{+\infty} a_k h^k \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} (\alpha^{k+1})^s. \end{aligned}$$

We have two cases to consider.

$$\sum_{s=0}^{n-1} (\alpha^{k+1})^s = \begin{cases} n & \text{if } k+1 \equiv 0 \pmod{n} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The first value of k that gives a non zero value is $k = n - 1$. Now we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{nh^{n-1}} \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} f(z_0 + h\alpha^s) \alpha^s &= \frac{1}{nh^{n-1}} \sum_{p=0}^{+\infty} n a_{n-1+np} h^{n-1+np} \\ &= \sum_{p=0}^{+\infty} a_{n-1+np} h^{np}. \end{aligned}$$

Passing to the limit, we obtain

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{nh^{n-1}} \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} f(z_0 + h\alpha^s) \alpha^s = a_{n-1} = \frac{f^{(n-1)}(z_0)}{(n-1)!}.$$

■

Theorem 28 (The discrete Morera theorem) *Let f be a continuous function on an open set U in the complex plane. If we have for some $n_0 \geq 2$*

$$\forall n \geq n_0, \forall z \in U, \forall \rho \in \mathbb{R}_+ \text{ such that } C_{z,\rho} \subset U, \quad \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} f(z + \rho \alpha^k) \alpha^k = 0, \quad (107)$$

then f is a polynomial of degree less or equal to $n_0 - 2$ in U .

Proof. From the theorem (25), if f is a continuous function in U and satisfies the discrete null sum properties, then f has a null integral on any circle inside the domain U . The Morera theorem assume then that f is holomorphic on U . Next we can apply the theorem (27) and we get that for any $n \geq n_0$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{nh^{n-1}} \sum_{s=0}^{n-1} f(z_0 + h\alpha^s) \alpha^s = 0 = \frac{f^{(n-1)}(z_0)}{(n-1)!}.$$

That means that f is a polynomial of degree less or equal to $n_0 - 2$.

■

Theorem 29 (The discrete Poisson formula for polynomials on the unit circle) *Let P be a polynomial of degree $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then, for any α roots of unity of order p , and any $z \in \mathbb{C}$ with $z \notin \{\alpha^m, m \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}\}$, we have the equality,*

$$P(z) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} P(\alpha^k) \frac{1 - (z\alpha^{-k})^{n+1}}{1 - z\alpha^{-k}}. \quad (108)$$

Proof. We obtain this formula from the expression of P in terms of its derivatives in $z_0 = 0$, where we substitute the derivatives by the associated discrete Cauchy formulas.

$$P(z) = \sum_{s=0}^n \frac{P^{(s)}(0)}{s!} z^s \quad (109)$$

$$= \sum_{s=0}^n \frac{1}{p} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} P(\alpha^k) \alpha^{-sk} z^s \quad (110)$$

$$= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} P(\alpha^k) \sum_{s=0}^n \alpha^{-sk} z^s \quad (111)$$

$$= \frac{1}{p} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} P(\alpha^k) \frac{1 - (z\alpha^{-k})^{n+1}}{1 - z\alpha^{-k}}. \quad (112)$$

If we choose $p = n + 1$, this formula can be simplified under the form,

$$P(z) = \frac{1 - z^{n+1}}{n + 1} \sum_{k=0}^n P(\alpha^k) \frac{1}{1 - z\alpha^{-k}}. \quad (113)$$

■

The last formula appears to be exactly the Lagrange interpolation formula on roots of unity. It thus appears that the discrete version of the continuous Poisson Formula on the unit circle is a discrete interpolation process on regularly spaced points on the unit circle. This lets us view the continuous Poisson formula as a continuous interpolation process on the unit circle. Using the generalized discrete Cauchy formula, we can generalize the previous formula to other circles.

Theorem 30 (The generalized discrete Poisson formula for polynomials on any circle) *Let P be a polynomial of degree $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then, for any α roots of unity of order p , any $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}$ and any $z \in \mathbb{C}$ with $z \notin \{\alpha^m, m \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}\}$, we have the equality,*

$$P(z) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} P\left(z_0 + r e^{2\pi i \frac{k}{p}}\right) \sum_{s=0}^n \left(\frac{z - z_0}{r}\right)^s e^{-2\pi i \frac{sk}{n+2}}.$$

We can also implement some parallel reasoning, that is transfer a reasoning from the theory of analytical functions to the discrete analog framework for polynomials. The maximum modulus principle, that says that, for any non constant analytic function and any disk inside its domain, the function can't achieve a maximum modulus strictly inside the disk, has a similar discrete maximum modulus principle for polynomials that can be deduced from the discrete mean property of polynomials.

Theorem 31 (The discrete maximum modulus principle for polynomials) *Let P be a complex polynomial of degree $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, and thus non constant. Then, for any circle $C_{z_0, \rho}$, centered in z_0 and of radius $\rho \neq 0$, and for any α , a primitive root of unity of order N strictly greater than n ,*

$$|P(z_0)| < \max_{i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}} |P(z_0 + \rho \alpha^i)| \quad (114)$$

and for any polynomial, if

$$|P(z_0)| = \max_{i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}} |P(z_0 + \rho \alpha^i)| \quad (115)$$

then P is constant.

Proof. This inequality is a straightforward consequence of the discrete mean formula for polynomials or the generalized Cauchy's formula.

■

We can extend the previous result with a discrete local minimum modulus principle.

Theorem 32 (The discrete minimum modulus principle for polynomials) *Let P be a complex polynomial of degree less than or equal to $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$ and z_0 such that $P(z_0) \neq 0$. We note*

$$P(z) = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i (z - z_0)^i.$$

Let $1 \leq k \leq n$ be the smallest non-null integer such that $a_k \neq 0$. Then, for any primitive root of unity α of order N strictly greater than n and satisfying $\frac{N}{\gcd(k,N)} \geq 3$, there exists a radius ρ such that,

$$|P(z_0)| \geq \min_{i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}} |P(z_0 + \rho \alpha^i)|. \quad (116)$$

Proof.

We begin by proving the inequality for $z_0 = 0$. We suppose that $P(0) \neq 0$ and $|P(0)| = \epsilon_0$ with $\epsilon_0 > 0$.

We treat the case where $a_1 \neq 0$. We set $L(z) = a_1 z + a_0$, the affine part of P , and $Q(z) = \sum_{i=2}^n a_i z^{i-2}$ such that

$$P(z) = a_0 + a_1 z + z^2 Q(z) = L(z) + z^2 Q(z).$$

We study the image of a regular polygon, centered in 0 and of radius $\rho > 0$, by the polynomial P . As a direct similarity, $L(z) = a_1 z + a_0$ transforms the regular polygon L of vertices $z_i = \rho \alpha^i$, $i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, in a regular polygon L' of vertices $L(z_i) = z'_i = a_1 z_i + a_0$, $i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, whose center is $P(0) = a_0$ and radius $\rho |a_1|$. The constraint $\rho < \frac{\epsilon_0}{|a_1|}$ ensures that 0 is not inside the circumcircle of the polygon.

Figure 3

Now we want to control the nonaffine part of P such that the shape of the polygon, whose vertices are $P(z_i)$, $i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, is close to the regular polygon L' obtained by the affine part of P . As a continuous function, the modulus of the polynomial $|Q(z)|$ is upper bounded on the closed unit disk by some constant M .

For any $0 < \rho \leq 1$, we have

$$\forall z \in \mathbb{C}, \text{ such that } |z| \leq \rho, \quad |P(z) - L(z)| = |z^2 Q(z)| \leq |z|^2 M \leq \rho^2 M.$$

Applying this to the regular polygon L , if $\rho \leq 1$ we obtain that

$$\forall i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}, \quad |P(z_i) - z'_i| \leq \rho^2 M.$$

This let us confine each value $P(z_i)$ in circle as small as we want and each centered in z'_i .

This step consists in making sure that at least one value $P(z_i)$ lies strictly in the circle $C_{(0, \epsilon_0)}$. The worst case occurs when 0 is in W on the circle $C_{(P(0), \rho|a_1|)}$, that is if $\rho|a_1| = \epsilon_0 = |a_0|$, but we avoid this case when we take $\rho < \rho_1$. Nevertheless, the worst case is interesting to understand the part of the circle where we expect to have a value z'_i and how we must manage it's neighbour $P(z'_i)$ to ensure that $|P(z'_i)| < |P(0)|$. In this worst case, we are looking at the intersection of two circles with the same radius $\rho|a_1| = \epsilon_0$, $C_{(W, \rho|a_1|)}$ and $C_{(P(0), \rho|a_1|)}$, and whose centers are also at a distance of $\rho|a_1|$. If we introduce the points P_1 and P_2 at the intersection of the two circles, the arc of $C_{(P(0), \rho|a_1|)}$, where one z'_i should be in such a way that $|z'_i| < \epsilon_0$, is the circular arc $\overline{P_1 W P_2}$. It has an angle of $\frac{2\pi}{3}$. This indicates that, for any regular polygon with 3 or more vertices, we will have a vertice z'_i such that $|z'_i| < \epsilon_0$. Now, to garantees at least one $|P(z'_i)| < |P(0)|$, we need more room around the worst cases P_1 and P_2 . Taking $\rho|a_1| = \epsilon < \epsilon_0$, the new circle $C_{(P(0), \rho|a_1|)}$ intersects $C_{(0, \epsilon_0)}$ in two new points P'_1 and P'_2 . Since the radius of the circle $C_{(W, \rho|a_1|)}$ is now smaller than that of $C_{(0, \epsilon_0)}$... P_1 and P_2 are strictly inside $C_{(0, \epsilon_0)}$. It lets open some space around P_1 and P_2 , so that, even if one z'_i is in one of these points, we can insert a circle, centred in z'_i and containing $P(z'_i)$, while staying inside $C_{(0, \epsilon_0)}$. At present, let's compute an upper bound for the radius for such a circle, that is, the distance between P_1 or P_2 to $C_{(0, \epsilon_0)}$. To support geometric reasoning, we draw a figure with the minimal information required and for the convenience of computations we set $\rho|a_1| = \epsilon = k\epsilon_0$ with a factor $0 < k < 1$.

Figure 4

From the equilateral triangle $(P(0), W, P_1)$, we have $IP_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} k\epsilon_0$ and $IP(0) = \frac{k\epsilon_0}{2}$. From the right triangle (OIP_1) we get $OP_1^2 = (\epsilon_0 - \frac{k\epsilon_0}{2})^2 + \frac{3k^2\epsilon_0^2}{4}$. The distance we are looking for is $MP_1 = \epsilon_0 - OP_1$ and finally $MP_1 = \epsilon_0 \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - k + k^2}\right)$.

A first method to find a bound for ρ that will ensure to find a minimum on the images of the vertices z_i is to choose $0 < k < \frac{1}{2}$. We obtain then usable lower bound for MP_1 . Indeed, we have, under this condition,

$$\frac{k}{2} > k^2 \quad \text{and then} \quad 1 - k + k^2 < 1 - \frac{k}{2} + \left(k^2 - \frac{k}{2}\right) + \frac{k^2}{16} < 1 - \frac{k}{2} + \frac{k^2}{16}. \quad (117)$$

This conducts to $MP_1 > \frac{k\epsilon_0}{4}$ or equivalently to $MP_1 > \frac{\rho|a_1|}{4}$. Now we are certain that if

$$|P(z_i) - z'_i| < \frac{\rho|a_1|}{4} \quad (118)$$

there will be at least one $P(z_i)$ such that $|P(z_i)| < |P(0)|$. To achieve this, using [] we just need to take

$$\rho^2 M < \frac{\rho|a_1|}{4},$$

and therefore

$$\rho < \frac{|a_1|}{4M}.$$

We can obtain a better bound if we analyse the derivable function defined on $]0, 1[$ by,

$$f(k) = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - k + k^2}}{k}.$$

$$f'(k) = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2}k - \sqrt{1 - k + k^2}}{k^2 \sqrt{1 - k + k^2}} = \frac{-\frac{3}{4}k^2}{k^2 \sqrt{1 - k + k^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}k + \sqrt{1 - k + k^2}\right)} < 0.$$

f being a decreasing function, the maximum of $f(k)$ is then obtained when k tends to zero and gives

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} f(k) = \frac{1}{2},$$

and it means that

$$MP_1 > \frac{k\epsilon_0}{2}.$$

This lets us take, in a similar way, the larger bound

$$\rho < \frac{|a_1|}{2M}.$$

We treat now the case were $z_0 = 0$ and $a_1 = 0$ and we note $k > 1$ the smallest non-null integer such that $a_k \neq 0$. We set $Q(z) = \sum_{i=k+1}^n a_i z^{i-(k+1)}$ such that

$$P(z) = a_0 + a_k z^k + z^{k+1} Q(z),$$

and we note $z'_s = a_0 + a_k z_s^k$ the principal part of the image by P of the vertice $z_s = \rho \alpha^s$, for $s \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and α a primitive root of unity of order N , where $N > n$. We observe that $|z'_s - a_0| = |a_k \rho^k|$ and don't depend on s . The z'_s are then on the same circle centered in a_0 . k being fixed, the distribution of the z'_s on that circle is described by the distribution of the $(\alpha^k)^s$ on the unit circle. From algebra, we know that in the cyclic group G of order N and of generator g , the element g^k generate a subgroup of order $\frac{N}{\gcd(N,k)}$. In the cyclic group of roots of unity of order N , α^k is of order $\frac{N}{\gcd(N,k)}$ and it's powers generate a polygon with $\frac{N}{\gcd(N,k)}$ vertices. According to the study of the previous case, we need a regular polygon with at least 3 vertices to be able to ensure that, for any α , we can tweak around with ρ to catch one $|P(z_s)|$ smaller than $|P(0)|$. If the condition $\frac{N}{\gcd(N,k)} \geq 3$ is satisfied, then we are in the same configuration as in the previous case.

$$\forall z \in \mathbb{C}, \text{ such that } |z| \leq \rho, \quad |P(z) - a_0 - a_k z^k| = |z^{k+1} Q(z)| \leq |z|^{k+1} M \leq \rho^{k+1} M.$$

For any $\epsilon_1 > 0$, we can set $\rho_1 < \frac{\epsilon_1}{|a_1|}$ and thus

$$\forall z \in \mathbb{C}, \text{ such that } |z| \leq \rho_1, \quad |L(z) - P(0)| = |a_1 z| < \epsilon_1. \quad (119)$$

Especially, for any primitive root of unity α of order $N > n$, we still have

$$\forall i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}, \quad |P(\rho_1 \alpha^i) - P(0)| < \epsilon_1. \quad (120)$$

But we can also use a rotation of the polygon to achieve more. We can rotate the z_i in such a way that one z'_i be on W , giving even more space for $P(z_i)$. In that case, since $|P(0) - W| = \rho|a_1|$, this lets us take the bound

$$\rho < \frac{|a_1|}{M}.$$

The search for a bound as large as possible may allow larger jump in iterative methods for the quest of a zero of a polynomial. We can give more computable bounds for ρ using the discrete maximum modulus principle []. ■

From this last result, we can deduce .

Theorem 33 *The Fundamental Theorem of Algebra, that is to say, every nonconstant polynomial P with complex coefficients has a root in \mathbb{C} , is a consequence of the discrete minimum principle for polynomials.*

Proof. We suppose that $P(z) \neq 0$ for all $z \in \mathbb{C}$ and is of degree $n \neq 0$. Since $|P(z)|$ is continuous it has a minimum for some $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}$. We have thus, for any radius $\rho > 0$ and any primitive root of unity α of order $n + 1$,

$$\forall i \in \{0, \dots, n\} \quad |P(z_0)| \leq |P(z_0 + \rho\alpha^i)|$$

and thus

$$|P(z_0)| \leq \min_{i \in \{0, \dots, n\}} |P(z_0 + \rho\alpha^i)|. \quad (121)$$

Since $P(z) \neq 0$, we look now at the values of P on a circle centered in z_0 and with radius ρ that satisfies the conditions (116) with a primitive root of unity α of order $n + 1$, where

$$|P(z_0)| \geq \min_{i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}} |P(z_0 + \rho\alpha^i)| \quad (122)$$

From the minimum modulus principle for polynomials, stated above, we deduce that P is constant. We obtain a contradiction and thus there must be a root. ■

So far, we have used univariate linear recurrence relations for polynomials, interpreting them in the Discret Fourier Transform to take the bridge to analytical functions. Before presenting numerical methods based on this tool we will end our algebraic perspectives with some multivariate aspects of the linear recurrence relations for polynomials.

7 The key stone of the linear recurrences and polynomials interplay

We have been playing with complex paths build on successive powers of one complex number. But we can extend our playground to any linear recurrences.

Theorem 34 *For any number sequence z_n in \mathbb{C} (resp. \mathbb{R}) and any polynomial P of $\mathbb{C}(x)$ (resp. $\mathbb{R}(x)$) the sequence $P(z_n)$ satisfies a linear recurrence in \mathbb{C} (resp. \mathbb{R}).*

Proof. The most straightforward argument is to say that the space of number sequences satisfying a linear recurrence is a subalgebra of the space of number sequences. But we need to deeply detail the operations involving both successive powers, when dealing with roots of order one, and the paths related to roots with orders greater than one. ■

8 Linear recurrences for multivariate polynomials

In the first place, there is a wide formulation for linear recurrent relations for polynomials.

Theorem 35 *Let A be a commutative ring. For any polynomial P of $\mathbb{A}[X_1, \dots, X_n]$, whose expanded form is written $P(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{i=1}^k a_i x_1^{i_1} \dots x_n^{i_n}$, where i is indexing the monomials that constitute the polynomial, we note $X_i = x_1^{i_1} \dots x_n^{i_n}$ and we work with fixed values. Then, P composed of k monomials, satisfies, from the recurrence relations for multivariate polynomials*

$$P(x_1^{s+k}, \dots, x_n^{s+k}) - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-i} \sigma_{k-i,k}(X_1, \dots, X_k) P(x_1^{i+s}, \dots, x_n^{i+s}) = 0 \quad (123)$$

Proof. Formally, the polynomial $K(t) = \prod_{i=1}^k (t - X_i)$ vanishes on each X_i 's and it's expanded form is

$$K(t) = t^k + \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-i} \sigma_{k-i,k}(X_1, \dots, X_k) t^i = 0. \quad (124)$$

We have for short notations

$$P(x_1^{s+i}, \dots, x_n^{s+i}) = \sum_{j=1}^k a_j x_1^{j_1(s+i)} \dots x_n^{j_n(s+i)} = \sum_{j=1}^k a_j X_j^{i+s}. \quad (125)$$

While replacing that in ref[], we get successivly

$$P(x_1^{s+k}, \dots, x_n^{s+k}) - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-i} \sigma_{k-i,k}(X_1, \dots, X_k) P(x_1^{i+s}, \dots, x_n^{i+s}) \quad (126)$$

$$= \sum_{j=1}^k a_j X_j^{k+s} - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-i} \sigma_{k-i,k}(X_1, \dots, X_k) \sum_{j=1}^k a_j X_j^{i+s} \quad (127)$$

$$= \sum_{j=1}^k a_j \left(X_j^{k+s} - \sum_{i=0}^{k-1} (-1)^{k-i} \sigma_{k-i,k}(X_1, \dots, X_k) X_j^{i+s} \right) \quad (128)$$

$$= \sum_{j=1}^k a_j X_j^s K(X_j) \quad (129)$$

$$= 0 \quad (130)$$

■

If we use this theorem for the polynomial $P(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$ we obtain immediately the power-sum formula of Girard-Newton [1, 7, 10, 14, 9, 3, 12] and [11] for a survey of the subject.

Theorem 36 (The Girard-Newton formulas) *The symmetric polynomials, with n monomials, noted*

$$s_k = \sigma_{1,n}(x_1^k, x_2^k, \dots, x_n^k) = x_1^k + x_2^k + \dots + x_n^k \quad (131)$$

and the elementary symmetric polynomials noted

$$e_k = \sigma_{k,n}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq n} x_{i_1} x_{i_2} \dots x_{i_k} \quad (132)$$

satisfy the recurrence relations

$$s_{n+j} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n+1-i} e_{n-i} s_{i+j}. \quad (133)$$

To show recurrence relations over the powers for other elementary symmetric polynomial, we give here the most simple cases. The coefficients of the recurrences are symmetric polynomials and thus can be expressed in terms of elementary symmetric polynomials.

Theorem 37 (Extended Girard-Newton formulas)

1. For three variables, let's denote the elementary symmetric polynomials by

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_1 &= x + y + z \\ \sigma_2 &= xy + xz + yz \\ \sigma_3 &= xyz,\end{aligned}$$

and we set

$$\sigma_2(k) = x^k y^k + x^k z^k + y^k z^k.$$

Then we have, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the linear recurrence over the powers for $\sigma_2(n)$,

$$\sigma_2(n) - \sigma_2 \sigma_2(n-1) + \sigma_1 \sigma_3 \sigma_2(n-2) - \sigma_3^2 \sigma_2(n-3) = 0$$

2. For four variables, let's denote the elementary symmetric polynomials by

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_1 &= x + y + z + t \\ \sigma_2 &= xy + xz + xt + yz + yt + zt \\ \sigma_3 &= xyz + xyt + xzt + yzt \\ \sigma_4 &= xyzt\end{aligned}$$

and we set

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_2(k) &= x^k y^k + x^k z^k + x^k t^k + y^k z^k + y^k t^k + z^k t^k \\ \sigma_3(k) &= (xyz)^k + (xyt)^k + (xzt)^k + (yzt)^k.\end{aligned}$$

Then we have, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the linear recurrence over the powers for $\sigma_3(n)$ and $\sigma_2(n)$,

$$\sigma_3(n) - \sigma_3 \sigma_3(n-1) + \sigma_4 \sigma_2 \sigma_3(n-2) - \sigma_4^2 \sigma_1 \sigma_3(n-3) + \sigma_4^3 \sigma_3(n-3) = 0$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_2(n) - \sigma_2 \sigma_2(n-1) + (\sigma_3 \sigma_1 - \sigma_4) \sigma_2(n-2) - (\sigma_3^2 + \sigma_4(\sigma_1^2 - 2\sigma_2)) \sigma_2(n-3) + \\ \sigma_4(\sigma_1 \sigma_3 - \sigma_4) \sigma_2(n-4) - \sigma_4^2 \sigma_2 \sigma_2(n-5) + \sigma_4^3 \sigma_2(n-6) = 0.\end{aligned}$$

For the case of bivariate polynomials, we can easily extend the mean theorem, the maximum modulus principle, the null sum theorem and the discrete Cauchy formula.

Theorem 38 (The mean theorem for bivariate polynomials) For any complex bivariate polynomial $P(x, y)$ whose maximum powers in x and y are respectively n and m , we have, for any primitive root of unity α of order strictly greater than n and any primitive root of unity β of order strictly greater than m

$$\frac{1}{nm} \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^m P(\alpha^i, \beta^j) = P(0, 0) \tag{134}$$

Theorem 39 (The null sum theorem for bivariate polynomials) For any complex bivariate polynomial $P(x, y)$ whose maximum powers in x and y are respectively n and m , we have, for any primitive root of unity α of order n and any primitive root of unity β of order m

$$\sum_{j=0}^m P(\alpha^i, \beta^j) \alpha^i \beta^j = 0 \quad (135)$$

Theorem 40 (The discrete maximum principle for bivariate polynomials)

Theorem 41 (The mean theorem for multivariate polynomials) For any complex multivariate polynomial $P(x, y)$ whose maximum powers in $x_i, i = 1 \dots s$, are respectively $n_i, i = 1 \dots s$, and any primitive roots of unity $\alpha_i, i = 1 \dots s$, of order strictly greater than $n_i, i = 1 \dots s$ respectively, we have

$$\frac{1}{\prod_{i=1}^s n_i} \sum_{k_1=0}^{n_1} \dots \sum_{k_s=0}^{n_s} P(\alpha_1^{k_1}, \dots, \alpha_s^{k_s}) = P(0, 0) \quad (136)$$

Theorem 42 (The null sum theorem for multivariate polynomials)

Theorem 43 (The discrete maximum principle for multivariate polynomials)

As a conclusion of this section, any multivariate polynomial verify a linear recurrence on powers, with coefficients the symmetric functions of it's monomials with alternate signs. For elementary symmetric polynomials, we can say a little more, since the coefficients of such recurrences are symmetric polynomials of monomials that are symmetric and for the elementary symmetric polynomial $\sigma_{i,n}$, the total number of terms in the equation is $\binom{n}{i}$.

To give an extended view of the usability of the linear recurrence relations for polynomials, we briefly present, in the last part, some numerical applications.

9 Numerical experiments

The examples we are presenting are not intended to build reliable algorithms at this stage. They are exposed as proof of concept and to illustrate the wide field of applications of the linear recurrences on powers for polynomials.

9.1 Euclidean division by linear recurrences

The euclidean division of two polynomials (real or complex) is easy to realize when the coefficients of the polynomial are known. Here, we just need to know the values of the polynomials to elaborate the euclidean division. For the example, we will give two polynomials by their coefficients to compute their values at some points.

Let $A(x)$ and $B(x)$ the two polynomials given by

$$A(x) = 2x^5 - x^4 + 3x^3 + x^2 - 5x + 1 \quad \text{and} \quad B(x) = 3x^3 - 2x^2 - 4x + 3$$

We search the polynomials $R(x)$ and $Q(x)$ such that

$$A(x) = B(x)Q(x) + R(x),$$

with $R(x)$ a polynomial of degree stricly less than the degree of $B(x)$. The degree of Q verify $\deg(A) - \deg(B) = \deg(Q)$, thus we set

$$Q(x) = ax^2 + bx + c.$$

But the constraint is that $A(x) - B(x)Q(x)$ must be of degree strictly less than $\deg(B) = 3$. We use the accorded recurrence relation to this constraint. We set

$$f(x) = A(x) - B(x)Q(x)$$

and the linear relations

$$g(x) = f(x^3) - (1 + x + x^2)f(x^2) + (x + x^2 + x^3)f(x) - x^3f(1) = 0$$

We just impose that $g(x_i) = 0$ for different values of x_i . We have 3 unknown a, b and c and thus we need 3 equations. Let's take

$$\begin{cases} g(2) = 0 \\ g(3) = 0 \\ g(4) = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} 50064 - 7224b - 504c - 72408a = 0 \\ 26765856 - 1325376b - 33696c - 39828672a = 0 \\ 2088737280 - 45904320b - 544320c - 3123852480a = 0 \end{cases}$$

The solution of the linear system is $\left\{a = \frac{2}{3}, b = \frac{1}{9}, c = \frac{53}{27}\right\}$ and recover exactly the coefficients of Q . We can now compute R in the points where we know A, B and Q , without computing its coefficients. To recover the coefficients of R , we can use the extended recurrences relations [] satisfied by R , for $s = 0, 1$ and 2 .

For $s = 0$ we have

$$f(x^2) - (x + x^2)f(x) + x^3f(1) = a_0 \prod_{i=1}^2 (1 - x^i),$$

which gives, with $x = 2$,

$$a_0 = -\frac{44}{9}.$$

For $s = 1$ we have

$$f(x^2) - (1 + x^2)f(x) + x^2f(1) = a_1(x - 1)(x - x^2),$$

which gives, with $x = 2$,

$$a_1 = -\frac{136}{27}.$$

For $s = 2$ we have

$$f(x^2) - (1 + x)f(x) + xf(1) = a_2(x^2 - 1)(x^2 - x),$$

which gives, with $x = 2$,

$$a_2 = -\frac{91}{27}.$$

We have finally obtained the true value of $R(x) = \frac{91}{27}x^2 + \frac{68}{27}x - \frac{44}{9}$.

The coefficients in the linear system may rapidly increase because of the powers. To overcome this aspect, it is possible to use complex numbers on the unit circle.

9.2 Greatest common divisor by linear recurrences

Let's try a similar method for computing the greatest common divisor of two polynomials. For our example, we take

$$A(x) = (3x - 2)(5x - 2)(-3x + 1)(2x - 5)(4x - 3)$$

and

$$B(x) = (-3x + 1)(2x - 5)(-6x + 1)(2x - 3)(4x + 1).$$

We search a polynomial Q , the missing factor of B in A with $\deg(Q) \leq \deg(B)$ and such that

$$P(x) = \frac{A(x)}{B(x)}Q(x)$$

is a polynomial. We set $Q(x) = ax^4 + bx^3 + cx^2 + dx + e$ and we build the constraint for P to be of the smallest degree as possible. We can try with degree 2, with relations

$$g(x) = P(x^3) - (1 + x + x^2)P(x^2) + (x + x^2 + x^3)P(x) - x^3P(1)$$

and ask that

$$\begin{cases} g(2) = 0 \\ g(3) = 0 \\ g(-2) = 0 \\ g(-3) = 0. \end{cases}$$

This system doesn't have non zero solution. We go further with recurrence for higher degrees. This time we ask that

$$h(x) = P(x^4) - (1 + x + x^2 + x^3)P(x^3) + (x + x^2 + 2x^3 + x^4 + x^5)P(x^2) - (x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6)P(x) + x^6P(1)$$

satisfies

$$\begin{cases} h(2) = 0 \\ h(3) = 0 \\ h(-2) = 0 \\ h(-3) = 0 \\ h(4) = 0. \end{cases}$$

This time we find the solutions $\left\{ a = 0, b = 16e, c = -\frac{68}{3}e, d = -\frac{8}{3}e \right\}$ and it says that the solution is the polynomial of degree 3

$$Q(x) = 16x^3 - \frac{68}{3}x^2 - \frac{8}{3}x + 1.$$

The greatest common factor is then

$$D(x) \frac{B(x)}{Q(x)},$$

where B and Q are both known. We can then use division or interpolation to recover D .

9.3 Exact reconstruction of a rational function by linear recurrence

Let f be a rational function given by

$$f(x) = \frac{x^3 + 5x^2 - 42x - 144}{x^4 + 3x^3 - 45x^2 - 59x + 420}.$$

We want to find back the exact expression of f from some of its values.

$$\text{We set } f(x) = \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}.$$

In a first, we suppose that the degrees of P and Q are known and that they are unitary polynomials.

Since $f(x)Q(x) = P(x)$ is a polynomial of degree 3, we search a polynomial

$$S(x) = x^4 + ax^3 + bx^2 + cx + d$$

and such that

$$g(x) = f(x)S(x)$$

is of degree 3. The linear recurrences satisfied for such a polynomial are

$$h(x) = g(x^3) - g(0) + (-x^3 - x^2 - x)(g(x^2) - g(0)) + (x^3(x^2 + x) + x^3)(g(x) - g(0)) - x^6(g(1) - g(0)) = 0 \quad (137)$$

We evaluate this formula for the different values of $x \in \{2, -2, 4, -5\}$. Using the values of f , we obtain the following linear system

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\frac{48133652}{22275}a - \frac{14697844}{22275}b - \frac{4636268}{22275}c - \frac{1490926}{22275}d - \frac{164352916}{22275} = 0 \\ \frac{1429812}{1925}a + \frac{447444}{1925}b + \frac{144828}{1925}c + \frac{6318}{275}d + \frac{5815476}{1925} = 0 \\ \frac{2098621857007872}{14287392977}a + \frac{599103902299392}{14287392977}b + \frac{178237149414912}{14287392977}c \\ + \frac{55606694021568}{14287392977}d + \frac{7824990358870272}{14287392977} = 0 \\ \frac{2043571123125}{52999936}b - \frac{2154491915625}{52999936}a + \frac{184908693375}{52999936}c \\ + \frac{193745594925}{52999936}d + \frac{27960639328125}{52999936} = 0 \end{array} \right.$$

This system admits for exact solution $a = 3.0, b = -45.0, c = -59.0, d = 420.0$. We retrieve $Q(x)$, the denominator of f . If Q is the denominator, then the function h obtained with this polynomial must be zero for any other x . This can be tested if necessary for other values for which f is known.

Several methods are available to us to reconstitute $P(x)$. We can proceed by interpolation, $Q(x)$ is at present known on the proposed abscissa. Else we can use the same method applied this time to

$$Q(x) = \frac{P(x)}{f(x)}.$$

We search $S(x) = x^3 + ax^2 + bx + c$, such that

$$g(x) = \frac{S(x)}{f(x)}$$

is a polynomial of degree 4. Such a polynomial must satisfy the linear recurrences

$$h(x) = g(x^4) - g(0) + (-x^4 - x^3 - x^2 - x)(g(x^3) - g(0)) + (x^7 + x^6 + 2x^5 + x^4 + x^3)(g(x^2) - g(0)) + (-x^9 - x^8 - x^7 - x^6)(g(x) - g(0)) + x^{10}(g(1) - g(0)) = 0$$

Let's recall that the coefficients for these recurrences are the coefficients of the polynomial whose zeros are $\{x, x^2, x^3, x^4\}$. To obtain them, it is sufficient to expand the polynomial

$$\prod_{i=1}^{i=4} (t - x^i) = t^4 + (-x^4 - x^3 - x^2 - x) t^3 + (x^7 + x^6 + 2x^5 + x^4 + x^3) t^2 + (-x^9 - x^8 - x^7 - x^6) t + x^{10}.$$

There are 3 unknown, thus we only compute recurrences for the 3 abscissa $x \in \{2, 4, -5\}$.

This produce the linear system

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\frac{69575728}{9405}a - \frac{12120034}{9405}b - \frac{7265023}{37620}c - \frac{422703616}{9405} = 0 \\ \frac{20984472360132608}{2151338175}a + \frac{2997957046688768}{2151338175}b \\ + \frac{797625802368128}{2151338175}c + \frac{135849949701275648}{2151338175} = 0 \\ \frac{5170806544184125000000}{308221324901523}a - \frac{1393708167414875000000}{308221324901523}b \\ + \frac{314413490014000000000}{308221324901523}c - \frac{391142331903293750000000}{308221324901523} = 0 \end{array} \right.$$

whose solution is $a = 5, b = -42, c = -144$. We have finally found $Q(x)$ and $P(x)$, so we have got $f(x)$.

When the degrees of P and Q are not already known, we can proceed by successive try with different choices for the degree of P and Q . We will find solutions for Q , but as soon as the degree of Q is too low, the fonction g is no more a polynomial and can't satisfy the recurrence everywhere. h will be no more a null function on other abscissa.

We can always suppose that Q is unitary, even if it means imposing an unknown coefficient for the dominant term of P . The coefficients of P don't intervene in the recurrence that determines Q , thus this has no consequence in the search of Q .

9.4 Rational interpolation

Given interpolation nodes, we search a rational function with smallest possible degree and that go through the interpolation points.

For our example we take the function $f(x) = \cos(x)$ to compute the nodes. We search for a rational function of the form

$$r(x) = \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}. \quad (138)$$

Then $r(x)Q(x)$ is a polynomial and must satisfy recurrence relations. It is necessary to know the function $r(x)$ on the successive powers of x_0 that stay in the recurrence. Let's take for example $x_0 = \frac{5}{6}$ for the nodes

$$\left\{ 1, \frac{5}{6}, \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^2, \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^3, \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^4, \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^5, \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^6, \left(\frac{5}{6}\right)^7 \right\}.$$

Now we choose P of degree 3. Without the knowledge of $r(0)$ we use the recurrences stasfied

by the function $g(x) = r(x)Q(x)$ which are

$$\begin{aligned} g(x^{4+i}) + (-x^3 - x^2 - x - 1)g(x^{3+i}) + (x^5 + x^4 + 2x^3 + x^2 + x)g(x^{2+i}) \\ + (-x^6 - x^5 - x^4 - x^3)g(x^{1+i}) + x^6g(x^i) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (139)$$

Each equation in the recurrence requires the use of 5 successive nodes thru the values of $g(x^i) \dots g(x^{i+4})$. We can provide powers up to order 7 for $g(x_0^i)$, that gives us the possibility to constitute 4 recurrence relations to allow us to compute 4 coefficient in a unitary polynomial. We set then

$$Q(x) = x^4 + ax^3 + bx^2 + cx + d \quad (140)$$

and we constrain the recurrence conditions to be satisfied for the given nodes with

$$\begin{cases} g(x_0^4) + (-x_0^3 - x_0^2 - x_0 - 1)g(x_0^3) + (x_0^5 + x_0^4 + 2x_0^3 + x_0^2 + x_0)g(x_0^2) \\ \quad + (-x_0^6 - x_0^5 - x_0^4 - x_0^3)g(x_0) + x_0^6g(1) = 0 \\ \dots \\ g(x_0^7) + (-x_0^3 - x_0^2 - x_0 - 1)g(x_0^6) + (x_0^5 + x_0^4 + 2x_0^3 + x_0^2 + x_0)g(x_0^5) \\ \quad + (-x_0^6 - x_0^5 - x_0^4 - x_0^3)g(x_0^4) + x_0^6g(x_0^3) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (141)$$

The numerical resolution of the system gives the respective values of a, b, c, d . We obtain finally

$$\begin{aligned} Q(x) = x^4 - 3.6386860443617715913x^3 + 25.840421251603621516x^2 \\ - 48.328194629553457647x + 289.21223042618916856. \end{aligned} \quad (142)$$

The knowledge of Q permits the computation of the values of P on the successive powers of x_0 . We limit ourselves to the 4 first powers to find P by interpolation with this values.

Graphical observations On the interval $[0.2, 1]$, we obtain a maximal relative error of order $7 \cdot 10^{-9}$.

On the interval $[0.26, 0.72]$, we obtain a maximal relative error of order 10^{-10} .

These encouraging results incite us to go further with, in mind, the goal to approximate a function uniformly.

9.5 Rational uniform approximation

The idea behind the following method of approximation is to conjugate two interpolation processes on two geometric sequences of nodes that converge at the two limits of the interval of approximation. The process is inspired by the quality of polynomial approximation at the nodes of Tchebyshev.

We expose the numerical method with the same function

$$f(x) = \cos(x).$$

This will allow us to compare with the rational interpolation previously obtained. We try to approach f by a rational function on the interval $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$,

$$\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}.$$

We fix the degree of $Q(x)$, $\deg(Q) = 6$ and we impose also $Q(0) = 1$. Q takes the form

$$Q(x) = 1 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3 + a_4x^4 + a_5x^5 + a_6x^6.$$

As in the interpolation method, we constrain the function $f(x)Q(x)$ to be a polynomial of a given degree de degré and through the recurrences on the values at the successive powers of a number x_0 we recover the constraints on the coefficients Q . However, as we can observe in the previous experiment with interpolation, with $x_0 < 1$, the powers are concentrated near zero and are not well balanced on the interval. So, we also take another geometric progression but one that tends towards the other limit of the interval $\frac{\pi}{2}$. We take P of degree 5 and we choose $x_0 = \frac{\pi}{4}$ at the middle of the interval. The constraints that are expressed at the successive powers of x_0 have the objective to control the function near zero, so we also wish that the limit of the interval is in the geometric progression. Let's remark for this that $P(x - (\frac{\pi}{4})^m)$ stays with the same degree as $P(x)$ and that its value in x_0^m is $P(0)$. We set $m = 9$ because of the powers used in the recurrence and such that this power is the last one that we use to mark both the end of the geometric progression and the limit of the interval. The function

$$g(x) = Q\left(x - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^m\right) f\left(x - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^m\right)$$

represents the polynomial $P\left(x - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^m\right)$ of degree 5. We must collect 8 equations to build Q . Nous keep only four constrains with polynomial recurrences on the powers of x_0 . These constrains are

$$\begin{aligned}
h(x_0) = & g\left(x_0^{6+k}\right) + \left(-x_0^5 - x_0^4 - x_0^3 - x_0^2 - x_0 - 1\right) g\left(x_0^{5+k}\right) \\
& + \left(x_0^9 + x_0^8 + 2x_0^7 + 2x_0^6 + 3x_0^5 + 2x_0^4 + 2x_0^3 + x_0^2 + x_0\right) g\left(x_0^{4+k}\right) \\
& + \left(-x_0^{12} - x_0^{11} - 2x_0^{10} - 3x_0^9 - 3x_0^8 - 3x_0^7 - 3x_0^6 - 2x_0^5 - x_0^4 - x_0^3\right) g\left(x_0^{3+k}\right) \\
& + \left(x_0^{14} + x_0^{13} + 2x_0^{12} + 2x_0^{11} + 3x_0^{10} + 2x_0^9 + 2x_0^8 + x_0^7 + x_0^6\right) g\left(x_0^{k+2}\right) + \\
& \left(-x_0^{15} - x_0^{14} - x_0^{13} - x_0^{12} - x_0^{11} - x_0^{10}\right) g\left(x_0^{k+1}\right) + x_0^{15} g\left(x_0^k\right) = 0 \quad (143)
\end{aligned}$$

for $k \in 0, \dots, 3$. This also explains that the choice of $m = 9$ is the one of the greatest power of x_0 in g , obtained when $k = 3$. We have now 4 equations. We proceed similarly in the vicinity of $\frac{\pi}{2}$. Thus we create the polynomial

$$P\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^m - x\right)$$

of degree degré 5 in x and that must follow recurrence relations on powers. So we set

$$h(x) = Q\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^m - x\right) f\left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^m - x\right).$$

h must verify the same constrains as g . Our progression stays geometric up to symmetry. We obtain then 4 new equations. The numerical resolution of the linear system of 8 equations with 8 unknowns provides the coefficients of Q . The numerical resolutions gives

$$\begin{aligned}
Q(x) = & 1 - 0.1088057934822138x + 0.0457166625830689x^2 - 0.004588471114201335x^3 \\
& + 0.001054992439137098x^4 - 0.00008080952634343964x^5 + 0.0000113471395370284x^6 \quad (144)
\end{aligned}$$

We can now compute the values of P . To preserve the symmetry on the constrains for P we proceed to an interpolation on 6 abscissa distributed at the ends of the two geometric progression, that are

$$\left\{0, \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^8, \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^7, \frac{\pi}{2} - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^7, \frac{\pi}{2} - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^8, \frac{\pi}{2}\right\}.$$

The polynomial interpolation can be done by linear recurrences or by any other usual algorithm. We obtain for this step,

$$\begin{aligned}
P(x) = & 1 - 0.1088057926343854x - 0.4542833492608689x^2 + 0.04981447456725641x^3 \\
& + 0.01986327771218818x^4 - 0.002320183984825627x^5. \quad (145)
\end{aligned}$$

Graphical observations With the obtained rational function, on the interval $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ have a maximal relative error of order 2.10^{-9} .

We can push further the method, by increasing the respective degrees of P and Q . For example, we choose $\deg(P) = 7$ and $\deg(Q) = 8$, with $m = 12$ and for P the interpolation on

$$\left\{0, \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^8, \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^7, \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^6, \frac{\pi}{2} - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^6, \frac{\pi}{2} - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^7, \frac{\pi}{2} - \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right)^8, \frac{\pi}{2}\right\}.$$

We obtain respectively for Q ,

$$\begin{aligned} Q(x) = & 1 - 0.1419983501563342x + 0.02712506898298892x^2 - 0.003834475493553242x^3 \\ & + 0.0003200812545027026x^4 - 0.00004568558025129268x^5 + 8.811991278336919 \cdot 10^{-7}x^6 \\ & - 1.974746378136301 \cdot 10^{-7}x^7 - 2.338784029456928 \cdot 10^{-8}x^8, \quad (146) \end{aligned}$$

and for P ,

$$\begin{aligned} P(x) = & 1 - 0.1419983501564864x - 0.4728749310140548x^2 + 0.06716469956350579x^3 \\ & + 0.02842421349706825x^4 - 0.004045045845259665x^5 - 0.0004178371188143792x^6 \\ & + 0.00006009568760378947x^7, \quad (147) \end{aligned}$$

With this last example, on the intervalle $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ we obtain a maximal relative error of order 2.10^{-13} .

For a last example of rational approximation of the \cos function, we choose $\deg(P) = 15$ and $\deg(Q) = 4$ and we use an interpolation scheme with a Tchebychev type distribution nodes.

We obtain respectively for Q ,

$$Q(x) = -0.0208764406015559x^4 + 0.184736077556478x^3 - 0.0779880320737342x^2 + 0.111560646869112x + 1.0, \quad (148)$$

and for P ,

$$\begin{aligned} P(x) = & -1.97567159465798 \cdot 10^{-10}x^{15} + 8.75584221388179 \cdot 10^{-9}x^{14} - 6.08142775064248 \cdot 10^{-8}x^{13} \\ & - 4.7294624304704 \cdot 10^{-7}x^{12} + 4.52029755521998 \cdot 10^{-6}x^{11} + 2.68164255701006 \cdot 10^{-5}x^{10} \\ & - 0.000253833074756242x^9 - 0.00073672290895188x^8 + 0.00754238825973852x^7 \\ & + 0.0057998303253803x^6 - 0.0877196783516029x^5 + 0.0597842420450004x^4 \\ & + 0.128955754131181x^3 - 0.577988032074436x^2 + 0.111560646869132x + 1.0, \quad (149) \end{aligned}$$

With this last example, on the interval $[0, \frac{\pi}{2}]$ we obtain a maximal error of order of 7.10^{-16} in python and $2.5 \cdot 10^{-16}$ in julia.

Changes in this release

- A version management has been added to simplify the tracking of successive changes.
- References have been added in the introduction.
- Correction: forgotten minus sign has been corrected in the statement of theorem (23).
- Correction: forgotten imaginary unit in the demonstration of theorem (25).
- We have added the proof of theorem (29).
- We have added the key stone theorem (34) and its devoted section, still in its early development.

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